

paper Chain

Comprehensive analysis of the existing
and emerging approaches of circular
economy models in pulp and paper
industry

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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Executive summary

Task T3.1 “Analysis of the existing and emerging approaches of circular economy models in PPI” is the first task of the work package (WP) 3 of the PAPERCHAIN project. This WP aims at designing the novel circular economy models of the 5 pilot cases developed within the project.

The objectives of the deliverable are the following:

- Present the concept of circular economy
- Review of business models for circular economy
- Analyse success cases of circular economy to identify key success factors and innovation challenges
- Describe the five circular cases of the PAPERCHAIN project and assess in which measures the previous findings can be applied

The purpose of the circular economy is to **replace the existing systems based on the linear economy “take, make, waste” with closed systems that reuse and conserve energy.** Circular economy aims at limiting the extraction of raw materials and the production of waste. It relies on four main principles: 1- food equals waste, 2- build resilience through diversity, 3- use energy from renewable resources and 4- think in systems. These principles can be translated into six business actions, composing the ReSOLVE framework: Regenerate, Share, Optimise, Loop, Virtualise, Exchange.

The factors that can help or slow down the implementation of a circular economy model, were identified and described in a PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technical, Environmental and Legal) analysis. These factors are represented in the figure below:

FIGURE 1: PESTEL ANALYSIS FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

In the literature, several studies present different circular economy business models. The five more common circular models were described with much details. They include:

- **product extension models**, in which products can be repaired by swapping out the desired components
- **circular supplies models**, in which resources are captured and returned to their natural cycle without harming the environment. Industrial symbiosis in which the residual outputs from one process can be used as feedstock for another process, are part of these circular supplies models. All the demo cases in Paperchain rely on industrial symbiosis principles.
- **Resource recovery models** focused on repairing and recovering the embedded value in products through innovative upcycling and recycling technologies.
- **Sharing platforms models** includes the shared creation, production, distribution, trade and consumption of goods and services by different people and organizations. It gives opportunities to consumers, companies and micro-entrepreneurs to rent, share, swap or lend their idle goods.
- **Product as a service models** offer services, product becomes simply the means to provide the offer. In other words, products are seen as distribution mechanisms for service supply.

A specific focus was given to circular supplies models, since all of the demo cases fit into this category. As a result, 5 examples of such models around the world were described, presenting the context, the system, the business model of a central key company, the benefits and risks and the best practices.

First, the **Kalundborg symbiosis** is one of the most ancient industrial symbiosis. The industrial park, located in Denmark, gathers eight companies and operates in closed loops for various utilities (heat, gas, water, etc.). More than 20 types of by-products are exchanged on a daily-basis.

Secondly, the **TERMIT symbiosis** in Slovenia provided a successful example of circular supplies model. In this case, industries producing waste give money to the TERMIT company (or to a waste manager) so that it is used secondary raw material (SRM) as construction products to realize geotechnical fills on TERMIT mining site. TERMIT as extra money and a material for the mining site instead of spending money to buy sands. The situation is also beneficial for the waste producers as they pay less money to TERMIT than for landfilling or incineration.

Thirdly, the business model of the **THREAD company** was presented. The company produces fibres and yarn using plastic waste collected in Haiti and Honduras by the local population. Thread initiative leads to high environmental and social benefits in these countries.

Fourthly, the production of the **Weber mortar** was described. This mortar, commercialised by Saint Gobain, uses aggregates from the Navigator company's boilers after improvement to replace a natural raw material. Once again, it is a win-win situation for all the stakeholders as, the Navigator company pays less money to Saint Gobain than previous landfilled costs. Saint Gobain receives extra money from the Navigator company and does not have to pay for natural material. A third stakeholder, the SME SACT, which plays the role of waste manager, has gained a new business.

Finally, the Enhance Landfill Mining (ELFM) concept is presented through the example of **The Closing the Circle (CtC) project** at the landfill of Remo in Houthalen-Helchteren (Belgium). It aims at recycling waste through material and energy recovery processes while limiting the volume of landfill and reducing CO₂ emissions.

To lay the groundwork for the two other tasks in WP3, the five demo cases of PAPERCHAIN were described, following the same structure: presentation of the project, stakeholders and value chain and benefits and challenges.

In the demo case 1 in Portugal, the types of **waste from the PPI the Navigator company, are used by the precast concrete producer SPRAL and the construction company MEGAVIA**. This demo case is supervised by the University of Aveiro.

In the demo case 2 in Spain, **ashes produced by SAICA, are used as alternative binders for soil stabilisation works in road projects**. ACCIONA is involved as waste manager and end-user and supervises the project implementation.

In the demo case 3 in Slovenia, **waste from the paper industry VIPAP are transformed into a composite material by DH company and used as backfilled material for slope stabilisation of a railway infrastructure**, operated by the Slovenian Railway – Infrastructure. ZAG is the appointed responsible for this demo case.

The demo case 4 takes place in Sweden in an industrial site in Domsjö. **Fibre sludge from Domsjö Fabriker are transformed into bioethanol and then to bio based cellulose and hemicellulose ethyl chloride by Sekab**. Finally, **Akzo Nobel uses the bio-based ethyl chloride to produce the polymer Bermocoll**. The project is supervised by SP Processum.

In the last demo case, also taking place in Sweden, **valorised Green Liquor Dregs provided by Ragn-Sells are used to produce a sealing layer for the mining industry Boliden**. SP Processum and LTU are in charge of the management of this demo.

During the analysis of these examples of circular economy models, best practices that could benefit to the PaperChain project were identified. They are presented in the following table. This list is not exhaustive and will be enriched in the next tasks of WP3 based on interviews of people involved in other circular cases.

Best Practices	How to implement in PAPERCHAIN
Proximity: Most successful circular model benefit from reducing transportation costs and increasing proximity of operation.	Map the potential partners around the area and assess their respective inputs and outputs to imagine circular partnership
Economic profitability: For full adoption, each circular model needs to be economically sustainable in the long term, especially if a large initial capital investment is required.	All business models must be economic profitability to be sustainable. No exception for circular model. Create scenario and prototypes to assess the economic potential of the solution
Self-organised: Many of the most successful partnerships	Revisit your partnership along the years

<p>have evolved organically over several years and local collaboration or fulfil a previously ignored circular model niche.</p>	
<p>Production design for by-product re-use:</p> <p>To avoid unnecessary costs and increase final product quality, firms should design their production systems to maintain by-product quality and prevent contamination.</p>	<p>Foreseen obsolescence should be prohibited and replaced by eco-design approach</p>
<p>New opportunity:</p> <p>Circular economy is a driver for innovation. Such approach may offer new opportunity (services, goods, partnership, etc.) and bring solution on multiple level: technical, economic, legal and environmental</p>	<p>Adopt a holistic point of view to imagine how circular economy can transform your company and your business model</p>
<p>Engage with stakeholders:</p> <p>Dialogue with key stakeholders is crucial to develop your branding, reassure investors and prevent some legal issues</p>	<p>Engage dialogue with the local community at an early stage of the project through focus group or visits</p>
<p>Contribute to a circular society:</p> <p>The circular nature of your business should not stop at the end of your production line. A circular approach integer the user experience in a “cradle to cradle” perspective. Such approach could lead to economic benefits</p>	<p>Adopt a holistic approach to integer your clients in the circular economy model developed by the company</p>
<p>Consider the social aspect of the circular business model implemented:</p> <p>Circular economy should not be only economically and environmentally driven but should integer a social dimension to be sustainable</p>	<p>Analyse your circular economy model under a sustainable development scope</p>
<p>Start thinking to the legal barriers as soon as possible</p> <p>Legal constraints can slow down the implementation of a circular economy model</p>	<p>Review legal constraints in targeted countries for the materials considered in the demo cases</p>

TABLE 1: BEST PRACTICES ISSUED FROM THE ANALYSIS OF RESOURCE RECOVERY MODELS

Introduction

PAPERCHAIN is a European project which started on 1st June 2017. It aims to deploy 5 circular economy models to create value from waste of 5 pulp and paper industries (PPI). The different waste streams will be converted into secondary raw materials for several resource intensive sectors: construction, mining, transport infrastructures and chemical sectors.

In the work package 3 of PAPERCHAIN, partners will design the novel circular economy models for the 5 circular cases. In the first task of this work package entitled “Analysis of the existing and emerging approaches of circular economy models in PPI”, the literature on circular economy will be reviewed to provide contextual elements, existing circular economic models and several examples will be presented. The objectives of this deliverable are:

- Present the concept of circular economy
- Develop a comprehensive review of existing literature in circular economy models in order to identify their characterisation including business models.
- Analyse existing cases of circular economy to identify drivers, barriers and innovation challenges
- Describe the five circular cases of the PAPERCHAIN project and assess which of the previous findings can be applied

The following figure portrays the integration of the main challenges addressed by this task as well as the position and expected outcome of this deliverable within the WP3.

FIGURE 2: OVERVIEW OVER WP3 TASKS AND THE POSITION OF DELIVERABLE

The main results of this first deliverable allow identifying those key elements that have to take part in the reference framework for new circular models to be developed in the following task of this WP.

The first section of this report provides a description of the circular economy concept and a PESTEL analysis to better understand the factors that can boost or slow down the development of circular economy. The second section presents existing circular economy models, explaining the strategies and identifying best practices. Each model is illustrated by several examples. The third section presents with more details 5 examples of industrial symbiosis. For each, the business model of a key / central company is represented and drivers, barriers and challenges are analysed. The review of existing examples and models, the identification of “dos & dont's” will enable the PAPERCHAIN consortium to better apprehend the elaboration of the circular economy models in the task 3.2. As a preliminary exploration, the five circular cases of the project are analysed and a first characterisation of them is provided in the last section of this deliverable.

1. Context for the Circular Economy

1.1. Review of the circular economy concept

Since the late 1960s, academics, thought-leaders, and businesses have independently advanced the circular economy concept into a vast network of practical applications in modern economic systems and industrial processes. The development of the field can be attributed to influential research reports, organisation development, and various schools of thought such as the performance economy, cradle-to-cradle, and industrial ecology, among others. The main idea behind the circular economy concept is that the linear model “take, make, use and waste” cannot last long for a growing population in a finite resource world. It is not sustainable since it uses more and more raw materials and resources and creates more and more waste. It becomes essential, to reuse and recycle, by working in closed loops materials or parts of products or products themselves, as shown in Figure 3.

The Objective of Circular Economy is to replace existing open production systems based on a linear consumption model, where raw materials are extracted, processed into finished products and become waste after they have been consumed, with closed systems that reuse resources and conserve energy. A circular economy aims at limiting the extraction of raw materials and the production of waste.

FIGURE 3: CONCEPT OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Adopting a circular economy model for a company, in opposition to a more traditional model, involves structural changes at different dimensions. A company with a circular economy model can follow one or more of circular economy dimensions, as presented in Table 2.

Business dimension	Linear economy	Circular economy
Design of a product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on customers' needs and use - Nice packaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Take into account the recycling process (pieces easy to change, repair, etc.)

Supply chain	- Rely on suppliers chosen for a mix between quality and price	- Based on recycling or using raw materials or waste of other companies
Business model	- Maximise profits	- Maximise lifecycle of a product
Logistics	- Mainly distribution system for customers	- Set-up a collecting service
Communication	- Developing a brand image	- Communication on circular economy - Encourage reuse, recycling, sharing of products

TABLE 2: DIFFERENCES BETWEEN LINEAR CIRCULAR ECONOMIES

One of the first mentions of closed loop material flows as a viable economic model was presented in 1966 in Kenneth E. Boulding's paper, *The Economics of the Coming Spaceship Earth* (Blewitt, 2015). Around ten years later, the Kalundborg Symbiosis was established in Denmark (section 3.1), which was one of the first closed loop interconnected production systems. Inspired by resource efficiency, Walter Stahel developed a research report for the European Commission in 1976 titled, 'The Potential for Substituting Manpower for Energy', in which he envisions a performance economy based on closed loops (circular economy), and its impact on job creation, competitiveness, waste prevention, and natural resource preservation. Then in 1982, Mr. Stahel created one of the first credible sustainability think tanks, The Product-life Institute, which focuses on promoting the circular economy through extending the life of products, minimising waste, and create cradle-to-cradle material flows (The Product-Life Institute, 2012). The circular economy concept was introduced into the European Union through Germany's environmental policy in 1996 with the *Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz (KrWG)*, a Federal German waste law designed to promote the recycling and protection of natural resources (Kunig 2003). Figure 4 presents the main steps that led to the definition and the promotion of the circular economy concept.

FIGURE 4: MAIN STEPS FOR THE DEFINITION AND PROMOTION OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY CONCEPT

Created in 2010, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation appears as a reference when talking about circular economy. Circular economy is inspired by living systems. In a living system, there is no waste, when something dies, it becomes a new resource for the members of the biosystem (animals, soil). According to the Foundation, a true circular economy seeks to rebuild capital: consumption only happens in bio-cycles, elsewhere there is no consumption, but only use. In the bio-cycle, resources are regenerated or recovered, with or without human intervention. In the technical cycle, human intervention recovers materials and recreates order using the energy available. To rebuild the capital, the two cycles go through different stages, as shown on the Figure 5.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY - *an industrial system that is restorative by design*

FIGURE 5: CIRCULAR ECONOMY SYSTEM DIAGRAM (ELLEN MACARTHUR FOUNDATION S.D.)

Copying living systems, a circular economy relies on four main principles (Peck 2017):

1. **Waste equals food:** this principle refers to the cycling of materials and products. In nature, there is no waste, a dead leaf becomes soil and provides nutrients to other organisms. Applied to a circular economy, it means that no input would be needed if we capitalise more on existing products, which can be seen as sources of materials.
2. **Build Resilience through diversity:** this idea means that companies, nations or economies can drag more value by sharing strengths. By sharing some resources

and support each other, they would be better prepared and able to resist to hard times of uncertainties.

3. Use energy from renewable resources: just like in nature, a circular economy should only rely on renewable energy, e.g. energy from sources that are naturally replenished on a human timescale. Using renewable energy enables to minimize impacts of an economic model.
4. Think in systems: people, ideas, places, companies and economies are interconnected. By considering these interconnections, new opportunities appear in terms of economic, environmental and societal gains. The concept of circular economy is not about one firm changing one product but about “many actors working together to create effective flows of materials and information” (Peck 2017).

These principles can be translated into six business actions, composing the ReSOLVE framework (McKinsey Center for Business and Environment 2015): Regenerate, Share, Optimise, Loop, Virtualise, Exchange.

Regenerate refers to all the actions that can be undertaken to restore the environment such as the using renewable energy sources and returning biological materials to the biosphere.

Share includes all the activities that maximise the use of a product between several persons. These activities include the sharing of assets such as for examples, rooms with Airbnb or cars with Autolib, the reuse of products through secondhand networks, and an extensive lifetime of products thanks to maintenance and upgradability.

Optimise is the idea of optimising the product but also the supply and the production chains. It corresponds to an increased performance or efficiency of a product, eliminating waste both in supply and production chains and developing the use of sensors and IoT to enhance the whole value chain.

Loop refers to the idea of working in closed loops by finding a new purpose to any product or material. In the biological system, loop corresponds to the anaerobically digestion and the extraction of biochemicals from organic waste

Virtualise corresponds to the dematerialisation of resource use. By providing virtually (such as book or music for example), less resources are required and the impact on the environment is minimised.

Exchange describes the processes of changing old technologies, materials or processes by new, upgraded ones and replacing old ways of doing things. In the automotive industry, combustion engines can be replaced by electric motors for example.

The six business actions and some examples are presented in Figure 6:

EXAMPLES

Source: Company interviews; Web search. S. Heck and M. Rogers, *Resource revolution: How to capture the biggest business opportunity in a century*, 2014.

FIGURE 6: THE RESOLVE FRAMEWORK

1.2. Factors influencing the development of a circular economy

The factors that can help or slow down the implementation of a circular economy model, are described with a PESTEL analysis. PESTEL stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal. The PESTEL analysis is a useful tool for understanding market growth, decline, business position, market potential and direction for operations. Thus, it has been applied to the concept of a circular economy as described in the previous section, to assess the factors having an impact on the development of such economy. Some of the factors are beneficial can be perceived as drivers. They are represented in **green** whereas other are detrimental for the development of a circular economy and appears as barriers; they are represented in **red**.

Political factors

A European circular strategy: The Circular Economy Conference on 9-10 March 2017 in Brussels was the occasion to launch the **Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform**. Presented as the “network of networks”, its objective is to go over the specifics of each sector to highlight cross-sector opportunities. As a forum gathering both knowledge and actors of the Circular Economy, the Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform relies on 3 pillars: engage policy dialogue between stakeholders; build a Coordination group to gather the actors of the Circular Economy; diffuse knowledge, national strategies and goods practises. This initiative sanctions the European Circular Economy strategy initiated in the 1980s and the 1990s. Even if this strategy is built according to areas and sectors specificities, it contains several inter alia measures (European Parliament 2016) such as:

- Communication and reports: e.g. communication on waste to energy
- Guidance and best practises: e.g. integrating waste management and resource efficiency in Best available techniques Reference documents
- Indicators: e.g. indicators to measure food wastes
- Support: e.g. improving the exchange of information between manufacturers and recyclers of electronic products
- Financing instruments: e.g. encouraging uptake of funding under the European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI) and cohesion policy funds for the circular economy

In addition to the measures and the different Directives adopted on waste, the EU action plan for the Circular Economy (*please refer to the legal section of the PESTEL*) enables the Commission to launch several initiatives.

Sector-specific initiatives: Plastic is ubiquitous in modern life, its production reaching 311 million tonnes in 2014 in the world, that is a twentyfold increase since 1960 (PlasticsEurope 2015). However, only a third of the plastic consumed goes straight to landfill instead of being reused or recycled. Beyond the economic loss, plastic landfilling has an important environmental impact: 400 million tonnes of GHG are emitted every year due to plastic production, which relies mainly on fossil fuel feedstock. Plastic is also responsible for environmental pollution. 5 to 13 million tonnes of plastic leaks into environment, seas and oceans every year. Over time, it impacts marine life and releases chemical additive and endocrine disruptors that enter in the global food chain.

To tackle both the low rate of recycling and reuse of plastics and its environmental impacts, the European Commission set up an initiative (European Commission 2017) that targets ambitious objectives:

- Decoupling plastics production from virgin fossil feedstock and reducing its life-cycle GHG impacts
- Improving the economics, quality and uptake of plastic recycling and reuse
- Reducing plastic leakage into the environment

To achieve these objectives, the Commission plans to improve the “framework conditions for investments and innovations” (European Commission 2017). Implementing a cradle to cradle strategy, European institutions target a better design of plastic products to reduce their toxicity and ease their recycling. Beyond these technical innovations, information is key to raise awareness and encourage responsible behaviour. Closing the loop of circular economy, this initiative that should be implemented at the end of 2017 will promote stronger incentives to collect, sort and recycle all plastics.

Another EU initiatives concerns reuse of **water**. Because of climate change effect and overconsumption, water stress has become a growing issue in Europe. Over the last decade droughts have dramatically increased in number and intensity to such an extent that 11% of the European population and 17% of its territory have been affected by water scarcity. Unfortunately, it is just a beginning. The 2007 communication on Water scarcity and Droughts (European Commission 2007) indicated that water scarcity and droughts episodes will be amplified in the future. By 2030, half of Europe's river basins will suffer from water stress and/or water scarcity.

In this context, EU institutions pushed for reusing treated wastewater as an alternative source of water supply. Today, over the 400,000 million m³ of waste water treated in EU every year, only 964 million m³ is reused. It not enough given the environmental, social and economic benefits associated with using treated wastewater. According to a Blueprint to Safeguard Europe's Water Resources (European Commission 2012), it has many potentials. First, it enables to alleviate pressure by substituting to water abstraction on catchment basin, rivers and phreatic table. It would also help to cover at least partially water consumption during peak demand. Moreover, considering the nutrients contained in treated water, it represents a formidable natural substitute for farmers who use chemical fertilisers. This environmental benefit goes hand in hand with a positive impact on climate change. Reuse water would imply less greenhouse gas emissions when compared to desalination or water transfer approaches. Finally, it could create job in the water industry.

To achieve such objectives, the Commission set up a specific Action Plan to be developed by 2016-2017. This initiative relies on 4 pillars:

- Integer reuse in water planning and water management. In addition to the Water Framework Directive and the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive that set up a policy framework for water reuse, best practises and recommendations were summarized in a guideline (European Commission 2016) to encourage Member States to better integrate reuse in water planning and management
- Define minimum quality requirements for water reuse in irrigation and aquifer recharge. To face the lack of a coherent and comprehensive legislative framework within the EU, the Commission proposed in 2017 of a common European target.
- Favour water reuse in industrial activities. The European Commission has the ambition to develop and review a Best Available Techniques Reference document specific to the water sector
- Support to research and innovation in water reuse. The European Innovation Partnership (EIP) on Water has been funding different initiatives to improve treatment facilities, develop smart technology and reduce energy consumption for instance. Other European budgets, such as the Horizon 2020 or the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, exist to promote investments in water reuse.

No specific circular strategy for the European paper industry: Except for the target of 90% recycling paper by 2025, **EU does not have a specific strategy that addresses the challenges of the paper industry.** Nonetheless, the Pulp and Paper Industry took action by releasing a European Declaration on Paper Recycling 2016-2020 in May 2017. The Confederation of European Paper Industries and other actors proposed a set of recommendations to promote a circular economy (European Paper Recycling Council 2017):

- Ban landfill for recyclable paper by 2020
- Implement a waste hierarchy
- Reprimand countries where commingled collection continues to exist
- Ensure that the increase in the collection of paper must be higher than the increase in the net trade of paper for recycling
- Review policies and legislation preventing paper products from being recycled

The CEPI and other actors are united in the European Paper Recycling Council. Together, they undertook activities to ensure quantity and quality of paper for recycling in the paper chain along the value chain. This consortium pledge for a strong cooperation between stakeholders which are involved along the value chain, to prevent waste during manufacturing, convert/printing and recycling processes. Aware of the necessity of energy efficient fabrication process, the CEPI encourages research and development to reduce the environmental impact of the paper and pulp industry. In addition to an internal reorganisation, members of the Consortium consider that educating and raising awareness of consumers and public bodies is a priority to engage the whole sector on a sustainable dynamic.

The objectives of the PAPERCHAIN project and the ambition of the partners involved fit perfectly well with this industry self-initiative. Emulation could inspire both parties

Economic factors

Economic benefits from circular economy: A recent report from McKinsey for the Ellen Mac Arthur Foundation shows that the technology revolution can create a net benefit of €1.8 billion per year by 2030 when implementing circular economy models, which is **€0.9 trillion more per year if current linear models are implemented** (McKinsey Center for Business and Environment 2015).

Structural changes involved: the transition between a linear model to a circular model requires important changes within a company. Indeed, a new value chain must be organised to implement a collection or a repairing service for example. Moving from a linear to a circular model involves also to make the employees' mentality evolve: new designs, long-term strategy and impacts for the products must be taken into account on a daily basis.

Lack of financial incentives: when developing a circular economy del from a linear one, important investments are required. Especially for the structural changes described above. No specific financial incentives are put in place in Europe today to encourage companies to change their traditional model.

Social factors

Increased population / demand: the current world population of 7,3 billion people is expected to reach 8,5 billion in 2030 and 9,7 billion in 2050. To face the demand of this growing population with limited resources, new consumptions patterns must be found (United Nations 2015).

Change of mentalities: the linear model "make, take, waste" is so much fixed in customers' mind that it might be difficult to make them adopt a new way of consuming, for example by sharing items, or by buying second hand-products made from recycling.

Data privacy: sharing raw materials and supply streams, giving away or selling by-products, and providing used items can be synonymous of revealing key and confidential information for industrials on their stocks, production and consumption.

Increased environmental consciousness: On a global scale, awareness for the protection of environment is increasing. According to Steven Cohen, Executive Director at Columbia University's Earth Institute, there are two reasons for this: the objective degradation of environmental conditions that people can see - such as smog in China, or landslides, and a growing emphasis on health and wellness (Cohen 2014). This growing interest for more sustainability will help circular models being accepted.

Technical factors

New technologies enabling circular models: Novel technologies provide the turnkey solution to decoupling economic growth and ecological degradation. New research fields are developing and will enable circular resource production consumption patterns in a short timeframe. They are presented in Table 3.

Technology	Potential Applications
Advanced recycling technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher recycling rates - More recycling opportunities
Life and Material Sciences Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New raw materials - Companies can replace their non-renewable inputs with a renewable feedstock - Nano-materials are also playing an increasing role in the switch to sustainable technologies, in the energy sector - New usages of industries' by-products
Sensor Technology and The Internet of All Things (IoT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measurable, recordable, and verifiable asset location making easier asset sharing, maintenance or replacement of a part of a product - Optimisation of waste collection routes
Block-chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart contract and digital ledgers through a fungible system designed for validity, transparency, and efficiency - Supply chain visualisation
Machine Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimised production processes based on the ebbs and flows of demand - Coupled with the IoT technology, machine learning can enhance supply streams in eco-industrial parks and reduce energy consumption - Effective transportation routes

TABLE 3: KEY TECHNOLOGIES ENABLING THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Products not designed to be recycled: when designing a product, companies don't think about end-of-life. Most of time, decisions are made according to different criteria such as cost of materials or customers' use and needs. The ease of recycling and dismantling

into smaller pieces to facilitate a circular economy is not enough taken into account.

Environmental factors

Increased scarcity of resources: In 2003, the European Security Strategy appointed the “competition for natural resources” a global challenge. In 2009, the UNEP Expert Advisory Group on Environment, Conflict and Peacebuilding explained that “as the global population continues to rise, and the demand for resources to grow, there is significant potential for conflicts over natural resources to intensify in the coming decades” (SWP Research Paper 2011). The circular economy, by relying less on natural raw materials and more on recycling of existing products, can help changing this situation.

Climate change: To respect the COP21 Agreement and keep global warming below 2°C, 50% reduction of total greenhouse gas emissions is required. According to a study from Deloitte, applying scaled circular economy strategies could meet 3/5th of this objective. Indeed, implementing circular economy models in the four key sectors: food, construction, automotive and electronics could reduce the CO2 emissions by 550Mt eq (Deloitte 2016).

Pricing not reflecting environmental cost: as most of time companies are not responsible for the end-of-life of a product, they do not include the “environmental cost” in a price. The price is set according to margins and costs. These costs can include manufacturing, design, supply, transport and marketing and communication but almost never the environmental cost for its end-of-life. As a result, customers are less sensitive to products that can be handled easily after their utilisation.

Legal factors

EU Commitment toward circular economy: Concerned by the high price of commodities and EU dependence situation, the European Commission developed a roadmap for a resource efficient Europe in 2011 (European Commission 2011). After the withdraw of a legislative proposal on waste, the Commission announced the launch of more ambitious proposal by the end of 2015. The Circular Economy package, Closing the Loop—An Action Plan for the Circular Economy, (European Commission 2015) aims at stimulating Europe’s transition toward a circular economy. It contains an Action Plan and several amendments on different legal acts.

Waste Framework Directive

This 2008 Directive introduced the main concepts of waste management including the ‘polluter pays principles’ and the ‘hierarchy of waste’ and the ‘end of waste’ status. The Directive set binding objectives to be reached by 2020 but the amendment goes a step further by defining share of municipal waste to be reused and recycled by 2025 and 2030 (Table 4).

Target	2025	2030
Share of municipal waste prepared for reuse and recycling	60%	65%
Share of municipal waste landfilled	/	10%

TABLE 4: PROPOSED WASTE MANAGEMENT TARGETS

Additionally, the proposal to extend the extended producer responsibility and the setup of economic instruments to implement the waste hierarchy.

Landfilling Directive

This Directive implemented in 1999 aims at banning landfilling of untreated waste and regulates the share of biodegradable municipal waste going to landfill e.g. 35% in 2016. The new amendment suggests to limit this share to 10% by 2030.

Packaging Waste Directive

To protect environment, this Directive implemented in 1994 required Member States to take measures to prevent packaging waste. The targets to be reached by 2008 were 65% of recovery and 55-80% of recycling of packaging. The Directive also set up specific objective for materials. For instance, the required recycle amount for paper and board was 60%. The amendment proposed new targets by 2025 and 2030 presented in Table 5.

Target	2025	2030
Share of all packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	65%	75%
Share of plastic packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	55%	/
Share of wood packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	60%	75%
Share of ferrous metal packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	75%	85%
Share of aluminium packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	75%	85%
Share of glass packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	75%	85%
Share of paper and cardboard packaging waste prepared for reuse and recycling	75%	85%

TABLE 5: SPECIFIC WASTE MANAGEMENT TARGETS

According to EU institutions, the proposal would enable economic and environmental benefits. Creating 170 000 jobs by 2035 and avoiding the emissions of 600 million tonnes of Co₂, these amendments would increase EU competitiveness and reduce its dependence.

Figure 7 summarises all the factors previously described in the PESTEL analysis.

FIGURE 7: PESTEL ANALYSIS FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

2. Circular Economic Models

2.1. Overview of the circular economy models

Having explained the most generic concepts, dimensions and taxonomy with regard to circular economy, this section aims at exploring research addressing the challenge of identifying **common patterns** in circular economy models. Several publications have appeared in literature, in consultancies' studies and different blog-posts related to the circular economy. Lewandowski (Lewandowski 2016) develops a comprehensive literature review of this subject, aiming to identify and classify the circular economy characteristics according to a business model structure. In his review, he identifies the main authors and researches related to eight dimensions: definitions, components, taxonomies, conceptual models, design methods and tools, adoption factors, evaluation models, and change methodologies. With regard to the "taxonomies" dimension, Lewandowski states that there exist several categorization schemes for business models in the circular economy. The value creation criterion represents the most popular way to categorise them (Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014), although there exist few other proposals based, for instance, on sources of value in a product-service system (Planing 2014). The existing typologies in literature are somewhat overlapping, and the distinction criteria are sometimes imprecise as Lewandowski points out (Lewandowski 2016). Thus, he proposes to merge all literature

sources that categorize business models in circular economy based on the ReSOLVE framework¹ (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2015).

In his review, Lewandowski (2016) provides a global summary of the different reviewed circular business model types systematized according to the ReSOLVE framework. For instance, as far as the 'Regenerate' business action is concerned, he identifies 5 business models with definition, sources and some examples: Energy recovery, Circular Supplies, Efficient buildings, Sustainable product locations and Chemical leasing (Lewandowski 2016).

In its report 'Circular Advantage: Innovative Business Models and Technologies to Create Value in a World without Limits to Growth', Accenture provides details of the five circular business models that were identified after the analysis developed of "more than 120 case studies of companies that are generating resource productivity improvements in innovative ways" (Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)². The outlined business models help companies operating in the circular economy, reach huge **advantages in resource productivity** as well as **creating innovative added value to customers** while generating benefits from reducing costs and reducing risks. They can be used alone or in combination, they are not exclusive to a specific scenario.

Those five business models will be taken into consideration for setting up the basis of our analysis of existing examples of circular models, thus, firstly a brief look at these models is provided in the following table (Table 6) but they are explained with more detail in the following sub-sections.

TABLE 6: FIVE BUSINESS MODELS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY. SOURCE: (LACY, KEEBLE, ET AL. 2014) (LEWANDOWSKI 2016)

Business model	Brief description	For companies that...	Examples
Circular supplies	Supply fully renewable, recyclable, or biodegradable resource inputs that support circular production and consumption systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deal with scarce commodities - Have major environmental footprint 	Royal DSM Nike - Flyknit technology
Resource recovery (Recycling 2.0; Recycling; ...)	It leverages technological innovations and capabilities to recover and reuse resource outputs maximizing their economic value	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recover the end of life products to recapture and reuse valuable material, 	US grocery chain Kroger Starbucks Ricoh

¹ See Chapter 1 for a detailed description.

² The analysis was developed in 2013-2014 covering more than 120 circular economy case studies that represented a wide range of geographies and industries in the high tech, textiles, automotive and consumer goods industries.

		<p>energy, and components</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recover waste and by-products from a production process 	<p>Walt Disney World Resort operated by Harvest Power</p>
<p>Product life extension</p>	<p>Extended usage of products and assets – wasted materials are maintained or even improved by repairing, upgrading, remanufacturing</p>	<p>Capital-intensive B2B segments (such as industrial equipment) and B2C companies that serve markets where pre-owned products (or “recommerce”)</p>	<p>Google - Project Ara</p> <p>Caterpillar's remanufacturing activity- Reman Program</p> <p>Patagonia</p> <p>Giroflex</p> <p>Bosh remanufactured car parts</p>
<p>Sharing platforms</p>	<p>Promotes a platform for collaboration among product users - the sharing of overcapacity or underutilization, increasing productivity and user value creation of assets with a low ownership or use rate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Their products and assets have a low utilization or ownership rate. - Specializing in increasing the utilization rate of products without doing any manufacturing themselves 	<p>Travel markets (Ride-sharing company Lyft, Inc.), Transportation (Lyft, RelayRides, BlaBlaCar), lodging (Airbnb), and neighbors helping neighbors (TaskRabbit, NeighborGoods).</p> <p>Peerby</p>
<p>Product as a service / Product Service System/ Servitization</p>	<p>The conventional buy-to-own approach is replaced by a lease or pay-for-use arrangement - products are used by one or many customers and product longevity, reusability, and sharing are drivers of revenues and reduced costs</p>	<p>Whose products have high operational costs and they have good ability to manage their maintenance</p>	<p>Michelin</p> <p>Philips</p> <p>Rolls Royce with Jet Engines (power by the hour)</p> <p>Xerox / HP</p>

Complementary to the review of Lacy et al., other two analyses were explored in detail. Three frameworks for categorizing the various types of circular business models help Goldmann outline the basics of the circular economy (Goldmann 2016). They are: departure in resource loops, value bases and business model archetypes. According to Goldmann, the ‘technical and biological resource loops’³ could provide companies with a useful tool to draw their own circular business model and they represent two areas in which companies can potentially increase their **resource efficiency**. ‘Four value creation bases’ encompass the second framework mentioned by Goldmann in her review and they relate to the **improvement of material productivity**. The first one is the **‘Power of the inner circle’** which relates to keeping products alive and operating for as long as possible and preferably with the original owner or user. The **‘Power of circling longer’** represents the second value creation base and refers to keeping products in as many consecutive cycles as possible and lengthening cycling duration (repair, reuse, or full remanufacturing). Examples of this second value creation base are soft drink cans or bottles in consumables goods sector or, refrigerators, freezers, washing machines and dishwashers of energy efficiency class B or better should be repaired rather than exchanged with new. The **‘Power of Cascaded Use’** transforms materials across product categories to offset the need for virgin material inputs and with the Power of Pure Materials, design better products to facilitate reverse logistics and maintain material quality. A good example of this third value creation base are textiles, as second-hand apparel, utilized in the furniture industry as upholstery and end as part of an insulation material for construction. Last but not least, the **‘Power of pure circles’** highlights the importance of uncontaminated material streams, since this is key to maintaining the quality of the materials which in turn extends product longevity and thus increases material productivity. Goldmann concludes her review pointing out the key factors that will help companies choose those bases (‘powers’ could be jointly applied) to be incorporated into a company’s new business models such as: particular trade and market conditions; focus, interests and values of the company; and, existing competences and capabilities (Goldmann 2016). As for business model archetypes (the third framework explored by Goldmann, the five business models defined by Lacy et al. (2014) are briefly described. What is most relevant is the interlinkages she identifies between the previous four value creation powers and the five models (see Table 7).

TABLE 7: INTERLINKAGES BETWEEN FIVE BUSINESS MODELS AND FOUR VALUE CREATION POWERS (GULDMANN, 2016)

	Circular supplies	Resource recovery	Product life extension	Sharing platforms	Product as a service
Inner circle			✓	✓	✓
Circling longer	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

³ Figure of CLOSING LOOPS IN THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY (Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2013). Towards the Circular Economy: Economic and Business Rationale for an Accelerated Transition, P.24 in [5]).

Cascaded use		✓			
Pure circles	✓	✓			

We found other research reference posted by Forum for the Future⁴ related to circular business models which proposes 5 additional business models to the five classic ones (described above) framed in the Sustainable Living Plan of Unilever. Forum for the Future and Unilever co-developed a Circular Business Model toolkit to support the company developing radically different products and services. These 10 different proposals of circular business models can **create value by decoupling growth from their environmental footprint**. The authors called them the 'Enabling Business Models' which "*are not circular in their nature but can boost the circularity of the other models*". The following table (Table 8) summarizes these 10 business cases.

Based on the review described above, the following sections will be devoted to provide more detail about the five common circular models. We will take into consideration for the best practices analysis the typology presented by Lewandowsky since the five classic circular models better fits with PAPERCHAIN's proposal for new circular economy models or at least, they could provide PPI sector with the appropriate toolkit to identify new several business opportunities.

In order to set up a common understanding of some of the definitions, criteria and terms related to business models, we have structured the gathered data based on a scheme for better describing not only the potential business models that have emerged within each category, but also the strategies that support achieving circularity objectives as well as the potential business models that companies could address in circular economy. The mentioned analysis is the following:

- A. A summary that covers general information of the model
- B. Different strategies and business models to all circular economy models
- C. Best Practices:
 - a. Main advantages:
 - b. Main difficulties / challenges
- D. Examples

⁴ <https://www.forumforthefuture.org/sites/default/files/Infographic.pdf>

TABLE 8: SUMMARY OF THE 10 ENABLING BUSINESS MODELS (SOURCE: (ROSE ET LEGRAND S.D.))

ENABLING BUSINESS MODELS	Description	Market Growth Opportunities
Closed loop recycling (e.g. Nike; North Face – examples of Closed-loop recycling + downcycling)	Using recycled products as raw materials to manufacture new products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure supply of materials • Reduced material costs /disposal costs • Improved reputation / brand equity (CSR); Increased marketing opportunities. Improved customer engagement (through more interaction points with costumers)
Downcycling (e.g. Collection Services - M&S Shwopping)	Turning materials from one or more used products into a new product with lower quality.	The same opportunities as in 'closed loop recycling' + <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower input costs as no extraction costs
Upcycling (e.g. Closed- loop recycling + upcycling examples – Method; HP; Worn Again)	Turning materials from one or more used products into a new product, implying an improvement in quality	The same opportunities as in 'downcycling' + <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased product value through recycling of lower value products
Industrial symbiosis (e.g. Timberland partnered with Omni United; DuPont and Procter & Gamble)	Sharing services, utilities and by-products among industries to improve resource efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Extracting value from material streams •Fuelling growth through cost efficiency •Ensuring business continuity by securing the supply of constraint raw materials •Lower costs of raw materials
Collection services (e.g. Nespresso; Beijing Subway Recycling Program)	Providing a service to collect old or used products.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer or industry partner pay for collection • Additional funding sought from local authorities • Secure supply of materials; Improved reputation/brand equity; Increased marketing opportunities; Improved customer engagement; Lower input costs as no extraction costs
Product service system (e.g. Splosh ; Philips - Pay per Lux; Lego – Pley)	Put the focuses on offering a solution rather than a product only. This leads to a marketable set of joint products and services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New revenue stream through service • Less material costs through dematerialisation • Product lock-In • Premium Price for Service

	that are capable of fulfilling a user's needs together.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure supply of materials; Improved reputation/brand equity (CSR) through improved customer service
Lock-in (e.g. gDiapers; Soda Maker; Brita fill and go; Replenish / Clean Path)	An offer that encourages consumers to carry on using a specific product or service on a regular base	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New revenue streams through service or product diversification • Increased use through contract • Long term contracts and customer loyalty • Pay per use • Premium price • Improves and ensures customer relationship • New and scalable marketing opportunities
Local loop (e.g. Natura Ecoparque)	As production processes are re-shored back into the countries where the business has its main markets, the local manufacturing loop becomes closer and benefits clustering of industries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More control and reduced risk to value chain interruptions • Lower logistics costs • Increased efficiency because of centralisation
Modularity (e.g. Google Ara; Electrical Toothbrushes; Bobble)	A design that divides a product into smaller parts that can then be independently created, used and replaced.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New revenue stream opportunities e.g. repair service/upgrades/replacement • Cost reduction through reuse of materials (parts replaced) • Price premium on parts must outweigh business benefit of selling full product • New service opportunities around parts must outweigh business benefit of selling full product • Improved customer relationship • Marketing opportunities through increased touch-points with consumer • Infinite services and updates opportunities around one product • Lock-in by product design
Personalisation (e.g. Geneu; Lyf Shoes)	Company creates data management opportunities that enable product personalisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fuelling growth through optimised (lean) manufacturing process • Charge premium for customisation or unique features only available through customised route. • Supply chain optimisation; Reduced disposal costs; Increased marketing opportunities and improved customer service through product personalisation; Improved reputation/brand equity (CSR)

2.2. Product-extension

The 'product life extension' model means being able to easily upgrade products or carry out repairs cost effectively. Just as the name implies, product life extension is all about making the useful life of a product as long as possible, maximizing profitability beyond the point of sale [6].

The profitability would be maximized over the products' lifecycle rather than at the point of sale as the product's useful life is designed to be as long as possible [Lacy & Rutqvist, 2015]

Summary:

It is important to integrate circular economy concerns at an early stage in the product design process through product life extension strategies: products are developed to endure, using components which can be upgraded, refurbished, remanufactured and resold.

This strategy allows products can be repaired by swapping out the desired components. It allows people to reduce the time between repeat purchases. Customers should be product owners rather than consumers by repairing their products. The profitability would be maximized over the products' lifecycle - the product's useful life is designed to be as long as possible.

Different strategies and business models to extend a product's useful life:

Product life extension STRATEGIES

Product attachment; Product durability; Standardization; Product pooling/sharing; Maintenance; Repair, Upgrade; Remanufacture	(Den Hollander et Bakker 2012) they built on research by (Linton et Jayaraman 2005)
Resell; Repair, Upgrade, Refill; Refurbish & Remanufacture	(Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)
Design for ease of maintenance and repair; Design for upgradability and adaptability; Design for standardization and compatibility; Design for dis- and reassembly	(Petroleum, Hughes et Cola 2017)

Potential Business models

a) classic long life - Business models focused on delivering long-product life, supported by design for durability and repair for instance	(Bocken, Bakker et De Pauw 2016)
b) encourage sufficiency - Solutions that actively seek to reduce end-user consumption through principles such as durability, upgradability, service, warranties and reparability and a non-consumerist approach to marketing and sales (e.g. no sales commissions)	

Main advantages – difficulties – challenges:

Difficulties

- PLE model changes the customer relationship dynamic dramatically – increases the number of potential interaction points with customers and deepens the customer relationship (Drewell, Five business models in the circular economy: #3 Product life extension 2014)
- Simply lengthening the lifespan of a product isn't enough - the customer should have an incentive to engage with the supplier throughout the entire lifecycle.
- It requires re-designing the product from scratch so that its performance can be easily upgraded by the supplier, or that repairs can be performed cost efficiently through a service or partner network.
- To find out what would be the optimal lifespan of your products, and which design option would be most favourable for the environment, a complete and robust assessment methodology like LCA is required. (Golsteijn 2016)
- “There are challenges with striking a balance between product life extension and technology innovation. On the one hand, promotion of the CE can extend product life, but on the other hand, it may limit opportunity for new innovation in technology.” (Naito 2016)

Challenges

- Design strategies that support the optimisation of product life and product life extension could be influential at institutional level - further research with other institutions is needed in order to identify barriers to and triggers for change in relation to households, industry and institutions. (Salvia, et al. 2016)
- Products do not need to last longer than a customer will use them - If a product's lifetime is longer than the user actually needs it, these extra resources are wasted (Golsteijn 2016)
- “Designers lack expertise to design for product life extension and product recycling”. He explores a range of product life extension strategies and concludes that tailored approaches are needed to better determine when to apply which product life extension strategy. (Bakker, et al. 2014)

Advantages

- All revenue streams are generated from upgrades, content and add-on sales. (Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)
- Industrial manufacturing companies have the biggest potential to decouple from dependency on constrained resources by innovating ways to extend their product's lifecycles.
- Positive impacts of encouraging sufficiency include the reduction in the consumption of resources, sustainable living and long-term customer loyalty, and new repair and service markets. (Bocken, Bakker et De Pauw 2016)

- Businesses may benefit from premium margins on high-quality products and high levels of customer loyalty.

MAINTAIN & REPAIR

- Most efficient way to restore the system back to normal working conditions
- Source of competitive advantage and business opportunity
- May generate more than three times the turnover of the original purchase
- Provides protection, pollution prevention, personnel safety and waste disposal

(Evans et Bocken 2014)

REFURBISH & REMANUFACTURE

- Remanufacture can be twice as profitable as manufacture
- Progression towards a "Green" company
- Reduce energy, material and negative environmental impacts of production waste
- Creates a market for skilled employment

Best Practices: Existing examples

Company	Example of product life extension
Interface	Interface – collecting and supplying fishing nets as a raw material for carpets. “Our commitment to Mission Zero® has fostered an entrepreneurial spirit inspiring innovative thinkers to imagine unique solutions. From the inventiveness of modular carpet itself to the advanced low impact products we offer today, Interface's history has been marked by innovation.”
Ricoh	Design for remanufacturing In 1997 it launched the first remanufactured black and white colour Multi-Function-Printer (MFP), and since then it has widened its products portfolio of remanufactured MFPs. The Ricoh Comet Circle underpins Ricoh's approach to sustainable design. In 1993 Ricoh developed its first policy on product design, for future reuse/recycling which includes, plastic grade identification, product strength design, reuse of high valued components, recycle of high quality grade materials, easy dismantling/segregation. This allows, for example, an adaptable outer plastic housing for easy serviceability (cleaning and quick drying) and avoids use of stickers/labels over multiple components for easy disassembly.
Caterpillar	By finding ways to extend the useful life of products, companies from Caterpillar to Wal-Mart are not only helping to keep discarded products out of the landfill, they're also discovering new ways to generate additional revenue from their

products - all without depriving their customers. Through this model, these innovators are weaning themselves off virgin resources by tying revenue generation to longevity instead of volume. Caterpillar's remanufacturing activity through its Reman Program, has focused in returning components at end of life to same-as-new condition or quality that reduces costs, waste, greenhouse gas emissions and need for raw inputs.

**BMA
Ergonomics**

Office chairs & Furniture - It designs products that are easy to disassemble when they are disposed of, enabling them to be easily recycled. Chairs for easy disassembly and remanufacturing as the seats can be taken off the frame within seconds. Chairs that go the extra mile

Most office chairs are on average decommissioned after ten years. However, many parts last for much longer. Axia office chairs can be refurbished by us after years of intensive use. The chairs are given an overhaul on site, with parts being replaced where necessary. The office chair is then as good as new and is ready for many more years of faithful service. This of course delivers major environmental benefits. After all, CO2 emissions in the usage phase are 0%.

Patagonia

Patagonia sells high quality, environmentally friendly outdoor apparel to outdoor enthusiasts who care about their environmental impact. The company relies on a number of different activities throughout its value chain to design out waste.

Patagonia's Worn Wear campaign encourages customers to extend the life of their Patagonia gear through proper care and repair.

Patagonia has partnered with iFixit, a DIY video tutorial site, to publish its own line of selfrepair videos for its clothing. This encourages customers to repair clothing instead of throwing it away and buying new pieces. The company also accepts clothing by mail to be repaired at its Reno Service Center.

2.3. Circular supplies

“This model allows companies to provide fully renewable, recyclable or biodegradable materials in its commercial processes”[17].

commercial processes”[17].

Summary:

CS model allows companies to provide renewable, recyclable, or biodegradable materials in its commercial processes to reduce costs and increase predictability and control. Companies providing circular supplies will be in greater demand as manufacturers desire an access to materials that are more circular and energy, which are less exposed to price increases and volatility. This model thus offers a competitive edge on demand.

This strategy focuses mainly on the biological cycles and refers to thinking of “waste equals food” in which resources are captured and returned to their natural cycle without harming the environment. The corresponding Circular Business Model Archetype ‘Circular supplies’ represents a business model based on industrial symbiosis in which the residual outputs from one process can be used as feedstock for another process.

Different strategies and business models for circular supplies:

Circular Supplies STRATEGIES

Design for a technological cycle

- **Cradle to cradle design** - A biomimetic approach to the design of products and systems. Based on nature’s processes it models human industry viewing materials as nutrients circulating in healthy, safe metabolisms
- **Resources passport** - An instrument that contains data about all materials in a certain supply chain to inform all actors with transparent information

Adapted from:
(Bocken, Bakker et De Pauw 2016),
(Bakker, et al. 2014)

Design for recycling in a linear economy

- **Downcycling** - Reprocessing materials into a product with a lower value than the original.
- **Cradle to cradle** (Product redesign to 100% closed material loops)
- **Circular sourcing** (Only sourcing circular products or materials)
- **Biomimicry** - Designs should allow for items to be easily dismantled and refurbished, without downgrading the material. Nature can also be used as a template for design, with the technique of biomimicry; for example, the pattern of a leaf can be studied to create solar cell models.
- **Blue Economy** - Cascading principle to make sure one’s waste is another’s income.

(Van Renswoude, ten Wolde et Joustra 2015)
(Kennard 2015)
(Pauli 2010)

Potential Business models

Adapted from:
(Bocken, Bakker et De

Cross-chain collaboration - Connecting and reinforcing a network of actors within their supply chain by managing transparency of data, transactions, material flows, responsibilities and sharing benefits

Pauw 2016);
(Bakker, et al.
2014)

Reverse logistics - Logistics to return of end-of-use or end-of-life products to manufacturers or other processing businesses, in order to facilitate reuse and recycling.

Main advantages – difficulties – challenges:

Difficulties

- Major upfront investments needed and limited access to funding: To successfully establish a circular supply chain, companies need to constantly monitor and optimise their product's lifecycle, in order to maintain value and performance of resources within the loop. Currently, funding is often limited to several pilot projects, which banks use to gain experience with circularity.
- Legal uncertainty associated with possible collusion: all parties in the supply chain have to be willing to collaborate. If there are forms of competition within the supply chain, collaboration amongst smaller suppliers or retailers might be hampered
- Linear technologies are still deeply rooted in our economy: change may not come so easily. Because linearity is so deeply rooted in our economy, many technological and institutional aspects are still tailored to this dominant model.
- Lack of sufficient differentiation between recycling and reuse at an institutional level: Policy makers invest significant financial sums as well as effort in incineration and recycling, but do not appear to invest in reuse and repair initiatives

(Avigdor, et al.
2014)

Challenges

- Regulatory factors can also encourage the demand for circular supplies
- Companies in some industries also need to take under consideration the CO2 emission right. As the costs of those rights are reflected in product pricing, the permit price is low relative to the environmental damage these emission cause. If the costs of emission right would be changed to reflect pollution's true impact, circular supplies model's interest would swell.
- Policy recommendations towards circular supply chains focus on macro level measures like a change in economic indicators, a shift towards integrated reporting by companies and taxation breaks for labour, which enable circularity to prevail over linearity

(Lacy, Keeble,
et al. 2014)

(Gayer 2011)

(Avigdor, et al.
2014)

- Companies are beginning to actively modify their strategies for recovery by changing from a more traditional supply chain structure to that of a closed-loop supply chain (CLSC) (Bocken, Bakker et De Pauw 2016)
- Learning to collaborate with new or unexpected partners, as well as shifting their strategies from operational based issues to value-creating systems (Florin, et al. 2015)

Advantages

- Energy and chemicals sectors are early adopters of the circular model. Bioenergy is the most mature industry sector, where significant interest has existed for more than a decade. Many chemical companies are changing over from fossil to bio-based supplies in order to make performance chemicals, platform chemicals, plastics, detergent, coatings, adhesives and more. (Erickson, Nelson et Winters 2012)
- Circular supply chains - The interviewed companies indicate that cooperation with grassroot groups and partnering up with companies that produce e.g. spare parts helped to develop their business. (Avigdor, et al. 2014)
- The rising population number and dropping natural resource reserves: By 2050, global resource use is expected to have tripled, while exploration and extraction costs are constantly rising. Apart from the environmental perspective, reduced resource consumption also poses financial drivers for companies to implement a circular supply chain. (Avigdor, et al. 2014)
- Societal developments are driving the spread of circular supply chains: From a socio-demographical point of view, increasing urbanisation is reducing the logistical costs associated with operating a circular supply chain. Changing consumer attitude is also driving adoption of circular supply chains.

Best Practices: Existing examples

Company	Example of Circular Supplies
Nike - Flyknit technology	Nike - Flyknit technology that creates a shoe upper out of a few single threads. It's less-wasteful (by 80 percent) and better-fitting and lighter—boosting an athlete's performance. Representing a win for the company, a win for the customer and a win for the environment.
Ikea	The retailer purchased a wind farm in Illinois as part of its effort to produce more renewable energy than it consumes by 2020. The project is expected to produce the equivalent of 130 percent of the energy used by all US Ikea stores. In total, 90% of US-based Ikea stores use solar energy produced from solar panels on store roofs, which

	helped Ikea meet 37% of its global energy needs with renewables in 2013
North European Bio Tech Oy	Developed a cellulosic ethanol in which agricultural residue is converted into renewable fuel. Local sawdust will be used as a feedstock. The cellulosic bio-ethanol created a new source of revenue for the company, while reducing emissions, creating jobs and strengthening national energy security.
Sugru by FormFormForm	FormFormForm developed a new material called Sugru, which allows customers to easily adapt, repair, or enhance their stuff property to make it work better. Sugru is a new self-setting rubber that can be formed by hand. It moulds like play-dough, bonds to almost anything and turns into a strong, flexible silicone rubber overnight
StayGreenOil	StayGreenOil hosts an online marketplace where users can list their used lubricants and cooking oil to sell to buyers instantly, without approvals or paperwork. StayGreen Oil applied for and was accepted into the Abbeton Accelerator Fund, a Sarasota-based business investment pool.

2.4. Resource recovery (efficiency and recycling):

This model allows companies to provide fully renewable, recyclable or biodegradable materials in its commercial processes [25].

Summary:

RR model is related to strategies that close resource loops. Its main goal is to protect the value of embedded components and material through a product's life cycle and to reduce costs of collecting, sorting and reprocessing.

RR strategies will be related to: a) preventing material leakage (eliminating/reducing material leakage from the production cycle translates into cost savings and increased efficiency); b) creating a closed-loop system (a product reaching the end of its useful life can be turned into something new or waste from a discarded product is the primary resource for developing a new product)

The resource recovery business model focuses on repairing and recovering the embedded value in products through innovative upcycling and recycling technologies.

Different strategies and business models for resource recovery:

Resource recovery STRATEGIES

Design for a technological cycle

- **Primary recycling** - Recycling process where resources retain high-quality
- **Tertiary recycling** - Breakdown of materials and products into their raw material components and successive build up to reach the properties of the original product or material
- **Upcycling** – A process of converting materials into new materials of higher quality and increased functionality

(Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)

Design for a biological cycle - **Biodegradation and composting**- Capability of degrading by biological activities where biological matter is decomposed by microorganisms.

Design for Dis- and Reassembly – it is about ensuring that products and parts can be separated and reassembled easily

- 1) **Recovering end-of-life products** to recapture value in closed loops (a company's own products) or open loops (any company's products)
- 2) **Recovering waste and by-products** from a company's own production process and operations to recapture value

(Gydesen, Maagoe et Hvidsteen 2016)

Potential Business models

Extending resource value - Using the residual value of resources (sourcing of otherwise “wasted” materials and resources to turn these into new forms of value).

(Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)

Industrial Symbiosis - Collaboration between industries involving the physical exchange of by-products, materials, energy or water which benefits from geographical proximity of businesses

Ecoindustrial parks - a specific form of industrial symbiosis in which a community of enterprises are located sufficiently close together that they can exchange materials, energy, and information, with the goal of improving their individual and overall environmental and socioeconomic performance

(Zhang, et al. 2016)

Resource Recovery Networks - clusters of consumer organisms that specialize in breaking down matter into simple nutrients, which can be used, again by consumers and producers alike. Formed by companies whose main activities are focused on recovery recyclable materials from waste flows, disassembling material components, remanufacturing or recycling

(Costa et Ferrao 2010)

Industrial Symbiosis' Networks - the development of symbiotic relations is characterized by being associated to 1) resource scarcity, which leads to an increase in symbiotic behaviour among species; 2) the exchange of services, such as transport or protection, not just materials; 3) the ability of strengthening community building, by providing anchors to the development of other species, and; 4) the range of connectedness between symbionts, from frequent and permanent to occasional

Main advantages – difficulties – challenges:

Difficulties

- Allowing IS systems to develop organically would arguably take too long (e.g. the IS of Kalundborg at least 25 years) - this time period clearly does not reflect 'urgent' development of sustainable industrial systems. Hence, pro-active strategies for IS, that are informed by an understanding of the social processes leading to the adoption of IS practices, are required (Velenturf et Jensen 2016)
- Many executives are still under the assumption that with recycling alone, the principles of the circular economy are in place - the circular principles are not fully understood. Harvesting parts from returned products delivers a higher value when reused in a service channel for repair purposes or remanufacturing practice instead of scrapping the product to receive the recycling value of the material. (Pheifer 2017)
- Commitment to Sustainable Development - Organizational strategy, goals, and performance measures have to motivate managers to develop and participate in the synergy projects, contributing to the company's and regional SD (Golev, Corder et Giurco 141-153)
- Information - the detailed qualitative and quantitative data on waste streams and local industries' material/water/energy requirements provide the starting point for the development of regional resource synergies
- Cooperation – the cooperation and trust between key players, sharing of information, and network development are crucially important factors for new synergy projects.
- Technical feasibility – a lack of technical knowledge within the industries may be an additional barrier for a new project.
- Regulatory – the uncertainties in environmental legislation and difficulties to obtain approvals for waste reuse projects from the regulatory authorities
- Community awareness (of the environmental and economic impacts that industries generate)

- Economic feasibility may result in increased revenue, lower input costs, lower operational costs, and diversifying and/or securing water, energy, and material supplies

Challenges

- Developing the industrial symbiosis will create a new way to improve product innovation, while new knowledge is gained bringing new businesses. (Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)
- New innovations help to reduce the overall operation costs and risks and help to achieve long-term resource security - Value can be captured through joint cost reductions (agreeing collaborative agreement for reducing costs across the networks)
- Social networks and innovation are identified as key themes to complement existing IS research - geographic proximity and trust between companies are essential for the realization of IS; however, economic geography could yet provide more insights into the proactive development of IS. (Velenturf et Jensen 2016)

Advantages

- Companies most sophisticated at 'Resource recovery' embed circular practices into the lifecycles of their products. They even reuse waste from other value chains in their production. And those that used to outsource waste management can now make money from it instead.. (Drewell, et , Five business models in the circular economy: #2 Resource Recovery 2014)
- Reduced costs of waste management
- Increased revenue streams from selling unwanted outputs
- Diminished environmental impact with lower demand for virgin resources and energy
- Convenient options for customers to dispose of unwanted products (Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)
- New interaction points between companies and customers where disposal and new purchases can be combined
- Deeper insights into how products are disposed
- In addition to exchanges of energy, the focus in IS is primarily placed on the exchange of waste and by-products - e.g., by reducing the costs of virgin raw materials or disposal costs and by the selling of the by-product. (Gabriel, Schöggel et Posch 2017)

Best Practices: Existing examples

Company	Example of Resource Recovery
IBM	E-Waste (discarded electronics) is a major problem for landfills, for example. Electronics can be difficult to recycle and many recyclers just

export e-waste to developing countries. IBM's end-of-life-management operations processed 32,000 metric tonnes of end-of-life pre- and post-consumer products. Out of these collected tonnes, IBM: recycled 54.9%; refurbished and resold 34.9%; reused 6.8%; sent 2.9% to waste to energy.

Impressively, that means only 0.5% was sent to landfills. From a life-cycle perspective, using recycled products reduces the need for raw materials to create the new product. It also reduces the impact of the initial product at end of life.

InterFace Net-Works™ An example of 'Extending resource value' – a program that sources fishing nets from coastal areas to clean up oceans and beaches while creating financial opportunities for people in impoverished communities and serving as a source to create recycled into yarn for Interface carpet

ECOVATIVE Ecovative produces and sells biodegradable materials, therefore contributing to the development of a circular economy. Ecovative Design LLC is a biomaterials company that produces sustainable industrial materials for a wide variety of purposes, from packaging to insulation and from building materials to automotive applications. What makes Ecovative unique is that instead of using traditional production techniques, the company literally grows their materials. This also means that the materials are biodegradable and compostable. Ecovative uses agricultural byproducts, such as corn stocks and seed husks, as a feeding ground for fungus. Ecovative doesn't actually grow mushrooms, but uses only the root structure of mushrooms, called mycelia.

AB Sugar An innovative business model example of internal symbiosis practices is the case of AB Sugar, who managed to reinvent its business model focused on sugar refining through innovation practices of industrial symbiosis.

Alueco According to VMRG :“AluEco stimulates sustainable construction/engineering. Participating organisations are obliged to realize recycling of aluminium. This ensures a guaranteed and sustainable use of aluminium. In addition AluEco uses modern technologies for front-construction of sustainable buildings. The members have committed themselves (by signing the agreement) to taking back (in case of demolition activities) the aluminium as an input for the recycling supply chain. AluEco supervises the process to make sure that the recycling activities will result in high value (construction) products with a minimal environmental impact.”

2.5. Sharing platforms

“By making it easy for people and companies to use idle products, these businesses are squeezing much more value from the resources used to make them” [33]

“Collaborative Consumption: the peer-to-peer-based activity of obtaining, giving, or sharing the access to goods and services, coordinated through community-based online services.” [34]

Summary:

The sharing platform model forges new relationships and business opportunities for consumers, companies and micro-entrepreneurs, who rent, share, swap or lend their idle goods. It includes the shared creation, production, distribution, trade and consumption of goods and services by different people and organizations. It is considered as a socio-economic ecosystem built around the sharing of human, physical and intellectual resources. In terms of impacts, it may increase impacts from the use phase while it cuts down on production and end-of-life impacts. Companies that leverage this model can maximize the use of the products they sell, enhance productivity and value creation.

The phenomenon of the sharing economy emerges from a number of technological developments that have simplified sharing of both physical and nonphysical goods and services through the availability of various information systems on the Internet. The main characteristics are: online collaboration, social commerce, the notion of sharing online, and consumer ideology.

Different strategies and business models for Sharing Platforms:

Sharing Platforms STRATEGIES

Recirculation of goods - second-hand and surplus goods markets	(Codagnone et Martens 2015)
Increased asset utilization - production factors markets	
Service and labour exchanges - labour market	

The platform can be coordinated either within a local community or network, or on a larger scale coordinated through community-based online services	(Hamari, Sjöklint et Ukkonen 2016)
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They identify seven distinct dimensions of sharing business models:	(Munoz et Cohen 2016)
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- platforms for collaboration
- under-utilized resources
- peer-to-peer interactions
- collaborative governance
- missiondriven

- alternative funding
- technology reliance

Potential Business models

<p>Crowd-based tech: Scalable solutions backed by a strong intermediary platform</p> <p>Collaborative consumption: Scalable models for resource optimization, although potentially less attractive models for outside investors</p> <p>Business to crowd: From carsharing to dress sharing, this model permits control not only of the platform but the resources to be shared. While the investment required for this model is greater than Type 1, it can still be scalable while permitting more quality control.</p> <p>Space-based, low tech sharing: Highly localized, low-tech, primarily space-based sharing</p> <p>Sharing outlier: Potential global impact on communities although attractiveness to traditional investors may be low</p>	<p>(Munoz et Cohen 2016)</p>
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Main advantages – difficulties – challenges:

Difficulties

<p>These platforms get picked up by users quite fast and have an ever-increasing popularity. At the same time, many of them struggle with their business model. It turns out to be hard to make these platforms financially viable.</p> <p>Sharing fits better in a new circular business model than in the old linear one. But how can we take other benefits into account, not just bottom line financial gain? We need to take a step back and assess how the new service contributes to decreasing a company's negative environmental impact and increasing its positive impact. That, in itself, can be seen as a service that creates value. The financial gain is not immediate, but with a step in between.</p>	<p>(Mieras 2016)</p>
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Challenges

<p>Even if the business case is clear, one question remains: is sharing also better for the (social) environment? In general, I would argue that for products with a high impact in the use phase, the effect will probably be smaller than for products with low impact in the use case.</p>	<p>(Mieras 2016)</p>
<p>The collaborative economy can lead to productivity growth and efficiency in a number of ways: by lowering marketplace transaction costs; by facilitating 'production' that is more efficient, allowing a greater level of output to be created from the same level of physical assets and labor; and</p>	<p>(Avital, et al. 2014)</p>

by creating production and exchange opportunities that were not previously possible.

It is also likely that peer marketplaces will be new engines for innovation, creating vast new 'micro-entrepreneurship' opportunities that empower individuals previously constrained by employment at traditional corporations.

There is no doubt that the burgeoning collaborative economy has benefited producers and consumers. However, there are several dark sides that need to be addressed before the collaborative economy becomes the real economy. This talk will highlight several issues such as regulatory arbitrage, tax avoidance, and the selling of public goods that are hindrances to social advancement.

The central issue in the collaborative economy right now is not the viability of sharing: how long these models can continue to work? This in turn depends on how workers are compensated.

Advantages

<p>The sharing economy combines benefits from economic, environmental and communal perspectives. Sharing enables more efficient and resilient use of financial resources, more efficient and sustainable use of resources and deeper social connection among people.</p>	<p>(Company 2014)</p>
<p>This business model provides a platform for product owners, individuals and organization to connect and share.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The benefits to users are increased flexibility and availability. - Customers can get an access to thousands of products at various price points and locations. - The business instead relinquishes ownership to the ecosystem. The value gained for businesses is not in owning resources but in managing the marketplace. 	<p>(Lacy, Rutqvist et Pagame, Waste to Wealth: The Circular Economy Advantage 2015)</p>
<p>Putting users together with owners creates entirely new revenue streams</p>	
<p>Shared sourcing platforms could also make it easier for companies to pool their purchases of materials with low environmental impact</p>	<p>(Vaughan 2014)</p>
<p>The non-economic social approach emphasizes the switch from ownership to access Perceived benefits include greener commerce, richer social experiences, community revival and strengthening of social capital.</p>	<p>(Codagnone et Martens 2015)</p>
<p>Economics commentaries see the sharing economy as a new source of beneficial competitive pressure and economic innovation. It could lead to an increase in productivity through use of underutilized assets or 'dead capital', create new markets through disruptive innovations and spur in turn further innovation among incumbent industries.</p>	

In the business and management literature the emphasis is on new business models expected to create new industries, revitalise traditional ones, create high quality jobs, and lead to a sustainable circular economy

Best Practices: Existing examples

Company	Example of Resource Recovery
Peerby	<p>It is one company that exemplifies this model. It operates a peer-to-peer borrowing service for a variety of products. As a start-up in 2011, the company wanted to build a platform that let individuals easily and safely share goods. It also wanted to create an online element that would incentivize people to participate in real life without being motivated by money. Peerby is active across all major cities in the Netherlands (where it has developed a critical mass of users) and Belgium, and is piloting its service in several US cities in preparation for a launch there. Peerby's goal is to expand to other countries as well and introduce an insurance product and other related services.</p>
3D Hubs	<p>3D Hubs offers a collaborative production platform for makers and 3D printer owners. Using 3D Hubs' platform, anyone with a 3D printer can bring customized, locally produced goods to those around them. By creating a platform that connects printing capacity with users who want to print, 3D Hubs makes the market of 3D printers more liquid and allows one printer to serve more people.</p>
Sendle	<p>Sendle is an online door-to-door parcel delivery service providing a convenient mechanism that links up new markets within the circular economy model by moving waste to a place where it becomes a valued resource. This successful start-up enterprise has grown quickly since its inception in 2014. Founder and CEO James Moody developed Sendle as a way to make his other online enterprise, TuShare, financially viable. TuShare allows clients to give unwanted items directly to receivers through an online sharing platform. Thus, Sendle came into being, first as the logistics mechanism embedded in the TuShare sharing network, but now it is a stand-alone entity and provides a way in which items can be delivered affordably and conveniently from door-to-door.</p>
Piggy Baby	<p>VALUE PROPOSITION: "Ride-sharing for goods. Convenient. Sustainable. Secure."</p> <p>MAIN CUSTOMERS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) People who need help in getting items delivered. 2) Businesses that need low-cost options for purchase delivery. <p>REVENUE GENERATION LOGIC – TWO OPTIONS:</p> <p>-Subvention-based: online businesses will pay Piggy- Baggy for using it in purchase delivery.</p>

-Transaction-based: end customers of second-hand online marketplaces will pay PiggyBaggy for using it in purchase delivery

Sharetribe

VALUE PROPOSITION: We make it easy and affordable for sharing economy entrepreneurs around the world to create and run their own online marketplace.

MAIN CUSTOMERS:

Sharing economy and lifestyle
Entrepreneurs

REVENUE GENERATION LOGIC: Customers pay a monthly fee ranging between \$39 - \$299. Fee depends on the number of members participating in the marketplace

2.1. Product as a service

“The basic premise of Product as a Service is that for many (most) products we purchase, it is the service provided that is essential, not the product itself.” [41]

“The customer is buying a desired function or performance instead of a specific product.”[9]

“The idea that goods are owned by consumers is outdated,” “As a consumer I am only interested in the performance of a product, not owning it. Sufficient light, comfortable seating, good audio and vision, that’s what counts” says Dutch architect Thomas Rau[42].

Summary:

A product-service system (PSS) represents an integrated bundle of products and services which aims at creating customer utility and value. A system of products, services, supporting networks and infrastructure that is designed to be competitive, satisfy customer needs and have a lower environmental impact than traditional business models. With this model product longevity, reusability and sharing are no longer seen as a risk but instead drivers of revenues and reduced cost.

PSS business model focuses on offering services and the product becomes simply the means to provide the offer. In other words, products are seen as distribution mechanisms for service supply. The competitive advantage emerges through the co-creation and co-production of activities among PSS providers, customers and value network partners.

Different strategies and business models for Product as a service:

Product as a Service STRATEGIES

Product-oriented - the business model is still mainly geared towards selling products but some additional services are added

(Tukker 2004)

Use-oriented services - the product stays in ownership with the provider, and is made available in a different form, and sometimes shared by a number of users

Result-oriented services - where the client and provider in principle agree on a result, and there is no pre-determined product involved

Potential Business models

- Product-related service (Tukker 2004)
- Advice and consultancy
- Product lease
- Product renting or sharing
- Product pooling
- Activity management/outsourcing
- Pay per service unit

Main advantages – difficulties – challenges:

Difficulties

"It would produce no useless and potentially dangerous waste; it could save manufacturers billions of dollars in valuable materials over time; and, because nutrients for new products are constantly circulated, it would diminish the extraction of raw materials (such as petrochemicals) and the manufacture of potentially disruptive materials, such as PVC, and eventually phase them out, resulting in more savings to the manufacturer and enormous benefit to the environment." (McDonough et Braungart 2002)

The key problem with these PSSs is the difficulty of agreeing with the user a set of good performance criteria, and the prediction of, or influence on, the behaviour of the user within reasonable margins. (Tukker 2004)

Creating buy-in and the learning curve. PaaS concepts can initially be time consuming and research intensive to establish and scale up, and come with a considerable learning curve at first. (Becqué 2015)

Access to capital and financing. The transition from selling products to selling services can have large financial implications. Revenues for product sales will not be realized upfront.

Accounting impacts. Current accounting practices can act as a barrier for PaaS on both the supplier as the customer's side.

Public sector challenges. Tendering rules don't always allow public sector agencies to 'purchase' PaaS contracts. Other challenges can be risk aversion by public procurement bodies, as well as confusion and logistical

challenges on the supplier side leading to insufficient clarity in their bids around the actual application of applying PaaS and subsequent product take-back

Importance of data and metrics. Solid data and metrics for defining the baseline, required performance level as well as to monitor actual performance under a PaaS contract are key to success in delivering a high quality service with a high level of resource and energy efficiency.

Legal challenges. Legal issues concerning for instance the legal ownership of a PaaS product can create challenges for contract implementation.

Take back and re-use. Companies will have to consider how the last part of their value chain affects the first part– components and materials contained in obsolete products once taken back have to be included again in a firm's own production process or be given a new life elsewhere.

Challenges

PaaS is quite common in some niche industries, such as car rental or airplane leasing where it has been around quite some time. Now the rise of technology and a new generation of consumers, that is financially strapped and environmentally conscious, provide opportunities to take the model to a greater scale

(Gydesen, Maagoe et Hvidsteen 2016)

It requires new ways of earning money compared to a traditional "make and sell" approach - Revenues will shift from a lump sum payment to a continued fees collected over the life of a contract or as the service is used. Due to the new kinds of revenue streams, this model requires the production cost to be paid for with upfront capital. In order to do so, companies' balance sheet must be in a level to be able to absorb.

(Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)

In cases where a product is used for a long period of time, the capital costs of depreciating the product over time and presenting those costs on to customers, may cause the overall offering to become too expensive. In order to be able to implement this business model, company could collaborate with a financial institution and mix the provision of the product with add-on services that create value for both parties.

(Becqué 2015)

Government bodies also have a key role to play by developing and implementing policies and programs that facilitate and create a favorable environment for resource-efficiency driven PaaS models, as well as through their influence in the market as a major procurer of products and services.

PaaS inspired business models may include a business-to-business marketplace, where companies offer their products (or even just components or raw materials) to the marketplace intermediary which subsequently (assembles and) markets the products through a managed product-service model to consumers. The marketplace can create

economies of scale, while the original supplier is bound by a take-back guarantee.

Advantages

It allows closer relationship with the customer - The company is able to innovate faster since understands their needs better. (Lacy, Keeble, et al. 2014)

Customers are able to reduce upfront capital expenditures while at the same time affording the manufacturer a continuous service revenue stream.

A company can reduce volume of raw materials, energy usage and waste generation

PSS model allows firms to create new sources of added value and competitiveness: (Tukker 2004)

- fulfil client needs in an integrated and customized way, hence allowing clients to concentrate on core activities,
- can build unique relationships with clients, enhancing customer loyalty, and
- can probably innovate faster since they follow their client needs better

The higher the level of servitization, the higher the positive environmental impact

PaaS business models have the potential to radically improve energy and physical resource productivity, delivering value against the least amount of (energy) resources (Becqué 2015)

With the supplier retaining ownership and responsibility for the product, there is a clear incentive to enhance the durability and efficiency of the product. Its residual value after take-back can improve profit margins, but also reduces the need for energy-intensive virgin material extraction and processing in the upstream supply chain while buffering the manufacturer from price volatilities due to increased resource scarcity.

PSS brings benefits to both sides of the value chain — customers and companies: (Barquet, et al. 2013)

Customers:

- More customized supply
- New functionalities and combinations of products and services to better suit customers' needs.
- Responsibility for monitoring and end-of-life transferred to the manufacturer.

- Higher total value delivered to the customer by increasing service elements.

Companies:

- New market opportunities and competitive advantages.
- Access to information about the product's performance during its use phase.
- Higher profit margins achieved by providing services instead of products.
- Strengthening customer relationships increases loyalty

Best Practices: Existing examples

Company	Examples of PaaS
Rolls Royce	<p>The Rolls Royce's 'power by the hour' - the company sells the hours their plane turbines are in the air. Instead of selling aero engines, Rolls-Royce now contracts with many of its customers for "power-by-the-hour". In essence the customer buys the power the aero engine delivers and Rolls-Royce provides all of the support (including maintenance) to ensure that aero engines can continue to deliver power. This shift in business model is important because it means the interests of clients and providers are much more closely aligned. In the olden days Rolls-Royce used to make money on time and materials - basically repairing engines. Put crudely the worse the engines were, the more maintenance they required, so the more money Rolls-Royce would make. Of course customers don't want unreliable engines that are always in the repair shop. They want reliable products that - in Rolls-Royce's case - allow planes to fly safely. (http://andyneely.blogspot.com.es/2013/11/what-is-servitization.html)</p>
Michelin	<p>Michelin pioneered leasing tyres under a pay-per-kilometre programme. As of 2011, Michelin Fleet Solutions had 290,000 vehicles under contract in 23 countries, offering tyre management (upgrades, maintenance, replacement) to optimise the performance of large truck fleets—in Europe, 50% of large truck fleets externalise their tyre management. By maintaining control over the tyres throughout their usage period, Michelin is able to easily collect them at end of the leases and extend their technical life (for instance by retreading) as well as to ensure proper reintegration into the material cascade at end of life [46]. Michelin, one of the world's leading tire manufacturers, has made significant strides toward adopting the Product as a Service model to create an innovative program in which fleet customers can lease instead of purchase tires outright. Under this program, Michelin effectively sells "tires as a service." Customers pay per miles driven. They don't own the tires. And don't have to deal with the hassles of</p>

punctures or maintenance of any kind. By adopting a Product as a Service model, Michelin is incentivized to develop longer lasting tires. And, by getting wornout tires back, the company is motivated to make sure through design and material selection that they can be reprocessed into a valuable input for new tires or something completely different. (Michelin Fleet Solutions, <http://www.michelintruck.com/michelintruck/services/MichelinFleetSolutions.jsp>)

Atlas Copco Group

Atlas Copco Compressor Technique is a global manufacturer of durable industrial equipment with a worldwide network of country sales-and-service subsidiaries. Atlas Copco's compressors are durable industrial products that represent sizeable investments for its customers and offer significant potential for the provision of related services. With more than 130 years of experience in product innovation, Atlas Copco has, in recent decades, extended its innovation trajectory into services. Beginning as a provider of spare parts, it gradually expanded its offering into a service portfolio that encompassed various maintenance services as well as total solution service contracts. Consequently, its innovative thrust in providing a variety of services related to its product offering has led to the development of an integrated product-service business model. The large multinational equipment manufacturer achieved consolidated annual revenues in excess of €3.2 billion (\$4.4 billion), with the service business amounting to approximately 40 percent of revenues in 2007. Its product offering encompasses an assortment of equipment types used for powering a diverse set of factory machines in a variety of industrial applications, such as power machines used to produce plastic bottles, textiles and automobiles.

Solar City Corporation

"Take control of your energy costs. We offer you the ability to predict and manage your energy use and spend. Our customers buy renewable energy from us for less than what they currently pay for electricity with no up-front cost. These advantages of solar power allow you to secure predictable, long-term energy rates to protect yourself from rising energy costs and price volatility." (<http://www.solarcity.com/commercial/solarcity-advantages>)

Philips

Philips sells lighting as a service, in which the company aims to reach more customers by retaining ownership of the lights and equipment so customers do not have to pay the upfront costs of installation. Philips also ensures the sound environmental management of its products by taking them back at the appropriate time for recycling or upgrading.

3. Current examples of resource recovery models

This section presents five examples of resource recovery model and/or industrial symbiosis around the world. This specific economic model of circular economy was selected because of its resemblance with the case studies of the PaperChain project. Each example is presented covering several aspects: context, business model, benefits and risks and, best practises. The “context” gives general information about the example while the “system” describes in detail its circular nature. The “business model” of each example is represented according to the Osterwalder canvas. This canvas was selected because of it is commonly accepted in the economic literature. The “benefits and risks” puts the examples in perspective by drawing up a report. Finally, the “best practises” corresponds to the main take-away messages that should be replicated in the PaperChain case studies.

3.1. The Kalundborg Symbiosis

Context

The Kalundborg Symbiosis in Kalundborg, Denmark is one of the first examples of large-scale industrial symbiosis. The eco industrial park operates in a closed loop system containing various industries, including energy, manufacturing, construction, healthcare, and agriculture.

It was developed out of casual conversations between a few enterprise managers in 1960 willing to improve their waste management system. Over time, the symbiosis grew to form a conglomerate of eight companies today. Figure 8 presents a map of the Kalundborg site currently in operation.

FIGURE 8: SYSTEM MAP OF THE KALUNDBORG SYMBIOSIS

System

The Kalundborg Symbiosis has become a textbook example of successful industrial symbiosis, displaying effective resource saving by **cycling waste, water, and materials within an industrial system**. The system operates as closed loop cycle between public and private entities buying and selling waste from each other for cost reduction and resource efficiency. **Products that can be physically transported from one company to another, such as steam, ash, gas, heat, sludge, and others are traded on a daily basis.**

The eco-industrial park was not planned, but organised itself organically through bilateral agreements between individual actors motivated by economic self-interest (Kalundborg Symbiosis 2017). The first by-product exchange in the symbiosis was the Statoil refinery, piping their excess gas to the gypsum factory, Gyproc. Since then, the industrial symbiosis has evolved organically based on mutual interests and the proximity of the company's employees. Now, forty years later, there are around **20 different examples of by-product exchanges represented in the Kalundborg symbiosis, which has been made possible due to the economic and environmental benefits that grow yearly and continuously for each party involved** (Kalundborg Symbiosis 2017).

The most relevant by-products to the PaperChain project are the reuse of fly ash and waste water treatment sludge produced by the Dong energy owned Asnaes power plant and the Novo Nordisk manufacturing plant respectively. Thus, **the exchanges studied in this section are between Dong Energy with Gyproc and Novo Nordisk with the local agrarian community.**

Some of the main stakeholders in the symbiosis are Novo Nordisk, Novozymes, DONG Energy, RGS90, Statoil, Gyproc, Kalundborg Supply, and KaraNoveren. Each company, except Novo Nordisk, operates in mature, low-margin, and high scale industries, such as manufacturing, utilities, and refining, so their success depends on their ability to innovate cost reduction strategies to lower their bottom line. **Each one of the stakeholders joined the symbiosis to gain a competitive advantage and increase operating efficiency.**

FIGURE 9: SIMPLIFIED KALUNDBORG INTERACTION WEB

The Asnaes Power Station is the heart of the symbiosis. It exchanges steam residuals to the Statoil Refinery for waste gas, which is used to generate electricity and steam. The power plant provides heat and electricity to a nearby fish farm, Novo Nordisk, and the rest of the community. Through the combustion of coal and orimulsion (bitumen-based fuel), the 1,300 MW Asnaes power station produces 170,000 tonnes of fly ash annually as by-product, which can be used in building and cement production. Additionally, the sulfur dioxide scrubber produced by DONG is transformed in gypsum as a by-product, which is sold to the wallboard company, Gyproc, to produce wallboard. Gyproc purchases the gypsum and approximately 80,000 metric tons of fly ash per year, which fulfils almost two-thirds of its demand (Ehrenfeld 1997). The fly ash produced by Asnaes plant is similar to the ash produced by SAICA for soil binders in road construction represented in circular case 2.

FIGURE 10: ASNAES & GYPROC SYMBIOSIS

From the Asnaes power plant, steam and energy are transferred to Novo Nordisk, a world leader in the production of insulin, enzymes, and penicillin. Novo Nordisk makes its product mix by fermentation, based on agricultural crops that are converted to valuable products by microorganisms. A nutrient-rich sludge remains after the products are harvested. Since 1976, Novo Nordisk has distributed the process sludge to nearby farms as a fertiliser.

After a heat treatment kills the remaining microorganisms, the nutrient-rich sludge is distributed throughout the countryside by a network of pipelines and tanker trucks. Novo Nordisk can only hold three days of sludge, but Novo Nordisk produces 3,000 cubic metres of sludge per day. Due to the high fines associated with sea or landfill disposal, the most cost effective solution was to donate the sludge to local farmers, free of cost. Novo Nordisk donates approximately 1.5 million cubic metres of fertiliser to the agricultural community annually (Industrial Green Chemistry World 2013). Three full-time employees coordinate its delivery. The sludge from the Novo Nordisk is similar to the sludge produced by the Domsjö Fabriker sulfite mill to create Bermocoll, a paint stabiliser in circular case 4 of the paperChain project.

Kalundborg Symbiosis

FIGURE 11: NOVONORDISK & FARMER SYMBIOSIS

Business Model

Because it is difficult to represent the business model of the Kalundborg symbiosis as a whole, it was decided to focus on the business model implemented by Dong Energy. The company owns the Asnaes power plant and plays a central role in this circular model. It is important to note that the figure below illustrates Dong's business model in the specific case of the Kalundborg Symbiosis.

<p>Key Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Member of the Ramase Laja program Network of trash collection center Processing company (ECSSA) 	<p>Key Activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect plastic trash Transform trash into flakes Process flakes into fabric Sell yarn and clothes 	<p>Value Propositions</p> <p><i>Thread international transforms trashes into dignified incomes and responsible outcomes</i></p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <p>B2C</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivery of Thread goods Publicity for partners' template made with Thread goods Circular model: consumers send products back to Thread when they are finished. <p>B2B</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivery of Thread goods 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>B2C</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proactive consumers informed about sustainable development and circular economy <p>B2B</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies that give attention to their environmental footprint
	<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic trash Fabric facilities 		<p>Channel</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web communication Blog Partnership with social organizations (Clinton Global Initiative) 	
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collection of trashes Transformation activities Shipping Fabric facilities Workforce Creation and maintenance of the website 			<p>Revenue Stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partnerships with clothing manufacturers Sell of goods to consumers 	

FIGURE 12: DONG BUSINESS MODEL IN THE KALUNDBORG SYMBIOSIS CASE

Benefits and risks

The various exchanges have resulted in **tremendous savings for the community and participating businesses**. The annual **water savings** total approximately 3 million cubic metres through reuse, treatment, and operational efficiency. The symbiosis **saves around 30,000 tonnes of coal and 19,000 tons of oil every year**. The **chemical savings** from the eco industrial park are 2,800 tonnes of sulfur, 80,000 tons of gypsum, and the fertiliser equivalent to the Novo Nordisk sludge is about 800 tonnes of nitrogen and 400 tonnes of phosphorous. Through various by-product exchanges, annually, 200,000 tonnes of fly ash/ clinker and 80,000 tonnes of scrubber sludge waste are exchanged from the Asnaes plant; 2,800 tonnes of sulfur as hydrogen sulfide in flue gas are avoided from the Statoil refinery; 1 million cubic metres of water treatment sludge are reused from the Novo Nordisk factory; 1,500-2,500 tonnes of sulfur dioxide and 130,000 tonnes of carbon dioxide emissions are avoided from coal and oil substitution (Ehrenfeld 1997). The estimated economic savings total US \$310 million (Teresa Domenech 2011).

Resource Saved	Savings	Actor
Water	3 million cubic metres	Entire Network
Coal	30,000 tonnes	Asnaes
Oil	19,000 tonnes	Asnaes/ Statoil
Sulfur	2,800 tonnes	Statoil
Gypsum	80,000 tonnes	Gyproc
Fly ash	200,000 tonnes	Asnaes
Sludge	1.5 million cubic metres	Novo Nordisk
Sulfur dioxide	1,500 - 2,500 tonnes	Asnaes
Carbon dioxide	130,000 tonnes	Asnaes/ Statoil

TABLE 9, ANNUAL KALUNDBORG SYMBIOSIS RESOURCE SAVINGS

However, the innovation challenges of such a system are:

- **Dependency within an interconnected system.** The production processes of each facility are so intertwined, if one production node has an error, it could create a bullwhip effect that could result in system failure. For example, if steam from the Asnaes plant stopped flowing, Statoil, Inbicon, Novo Nordisk, and Novozymes would all sustain significant production issues, which would have cascading effects on the rest of the eco-industrial park. To reduce this risk, backups and fail-safes are integrated within each by-product exchange.
- **Innovation stagnation.** Due to the interconnectedness of the eco-industrial park, the stakeholders risk being stuck in a certain mode of production that may be unsustainable in the long run and suffering from innovation stagnation. For example, the Asnaes power plant is the heart of the entire industrial ecosystem; it powers the entire symbiosis, and sells its by-products (steam and fly ash) to neighbouring factories. Thus forcing the entire community to run on coal power, which is a non-viable long-term solution due to pollution and supply concerns.
- **Quality Assurance.** The use of waste as a resource can be a production vulnerability if quality control is ignored. The National Academy of Engineering identified waste quality as a limiting factor in the reuse and recyclability of a product, and recommended the integration of manager quality control and function-quality monitoring systems into a company's supply chain (Richards 1997).

The Asnaes power plant has adopted these quality control systems for their fly ash and calcium sulphate production processes, which allow them to create synthetic gypsum with superior quality to mined gypsum, thus improving Gyproc's wallboard quality at a lower cost. Therefore waste quality control of by-products should be considered and integrated into the design and production process of the considered material.

Best Practices

The main four best practices that can be pulled out of this example are self-organisation, proximity, regulatory flexibility, and economic viability, which can inversely manifest as challenges if they are not represented.

- **Self-organised:** The symbiosis in Kalundborg manifested itself organically through bilateral negotiations over the past four decades. A “bottom-up” approach reduces a significant risk that can be present in a planned “top-down” eco-industrial park. If an industrial system is too carefully planned and integrated, the individual parts would be too closely linked and dependent on each other, rendering it fragile and liable to collapse in the event of a system failure
- **Proximity:** The proximity of the stakeholders played a crucial role in the development of the Kalundborg symbiosis. The cost reduction of infrastructure facilitated the material exchanges of by products through pipelines and near range trucking, paired with the proximity of the human partners contributed significantly to the cooperation needed to manage the operation effectively (Jacobsen, 2006).
- **Regulation:** The Danish regulatory framework has encouraged the evolution of industrial symbiosis in Kalundborg. Firms are required to be proactive; by submitting plans detailing their efforts to continually reduce their environmental impact, the Danish government can assist the symbiosis and provide necessary recommendations. Policies also support the symbiosis, such as the 1997 ban on sending recyclable or incinerable objects to landfill and tight water quality regulations. The members of the Kalundborg symbiosis were already in compliance with these regulations prior to their implementation, which allowed them to avoid the compliance costs and gain an advantage over their competitors. The eco-industrial park will also be at an advantage if any future regulations put limits on carbon emission, water pollution, or waste management practices. In addition, the Danish government has an open and accessible communication channel for regulatory concerns and questions, which helps firms and regulators establish goals. A more flexible, cooperative relationship is fostered between government and the regulated industries, and as a result, firms tend to focus their energies on finding creative ways to become more environmentally friendly instead of fighting with regulators.
- **Economic Profitability:** A key component to the success of the Kalundborg symbiosis was the short-term profitability of the project. Due to the business strategy scope of private companies, long investment payback periods could be a barrier to future industrial symbiosis projects (Jacobsen 2006).

3.2. The TERMIT Symbiosis

Context

The TERMIT case represents a successful example of a circular economy model. Located in Slovenia, this conglomerate gathers together local SMEs and large enterprises in order to recover waste and give them a second lease of life as construction materials for mining sites.

This initiative was called TERMIT Symbiosis in reference to the TERMIT company, a medium sized mining/processing company established in 1960. Its main activity consists in extracting and processing quartz sands for the foundry industry. The company is the largest producer of coated quartz sand and cover the most foundry market in middle in south east Europe. TERMIT's annual production of quartz sand is approximately 350.000 tonnes. Due to the surface extraction method, the company requires large quantities of materials to restore the surface of mining areas.

The circular nature of the model is based on **using different secondary raw material (SRM) as construction products to realize geotechnical fills on TERMIT mining site. SRM based construction products are produced as mainly mixtures of different recycled wastes and primary raw materials.**

System

In the TERMIT case, about 21 companies are cooperating in recycling materials for resource efficiency purpose. The solution implemented to realize the geotechnical fills on mining sites involves SRM products resulting from the mixtures of construction wastes provided by local partners and primary raw materials owned by TERMIT. This circular economy model was not facilitated by an external industrial symbiosis facilitator. The different stakeholders organised themselves through bilateral agreements aiming to economic self-interest.

On one hand, **companies producing waste give it away at lower price**, compared to giving it to a waste collector according to a more conventional model where waste is usually landfilled or/and incinerated. On the other hand, **TERMIT gains additional income for waste collection and reduces its extraction of primary materials for restoring the mining area.**

ZAG, a major institute in the field of building and civil engineering, has played an important role in **supporting the development of new building composites out of SRM.** The company has also contributed to the issuing of technical approvals of such products, which are not usually covered by regular and harmonised standards for construction products.

Two models are currently in place: in the first one, TERMIT has its own production of SRM based construction products. Currently the TERMIT company possesses 10 national technical approvals for SRM based construction products from mixture of different types

of wastes under different names such as (TERSAN TR, TERSAN S...). In the second one, companies producing waste, establish their own production of SRM based construction products on their site and sell made mixtures to TERMIT for geotechnical works. For example, the slag treating company HARSCO MINERALI sells ladle slag based composite EKOMINIT to TERMIT. All products benefit from compliance “system 1+” meaning that these materials are carefully inspected by notified product certification bodies. Their compliance with regulation for landfilling of inert wastes (the latter is applied since Slovenia has no legislation for leaching values for construction products) is particularly analysed.

Figure 13 presents some of the different stakeholders involved in the TERMIT case.

FIGURE 13: THE TERMIT CIRCULAR MODEL

With TERMIT as final user, some of the main stakeholders in the symbiosis are TE-TOL (thermal power plant with delivering to TERMIT their ashes and slags from incineration of coal and biomass), KNAUF (producer of thermal insulation delivering to TERMIT their waste of rockwool); ETI Izlake (producer of electrical protection devices delivering to TERMIT ceramic waste from production of electrical protection devices), Papirnica Vevče (paper producer delivering with remaining waste in the form of sludge), CIMOS (foundry delivering with waste foundry sand), HARSCO MINERALI (delivering composite EKOMINIT based on ladle slag from the steel company ACRONI) and others. Some of these industries are SME while others are large processing companies.

Figure 14 shows the effects of the implementation of the circular model.

Linear model: - TERMIT use **primary materials (sand)** for restoring the mining area
 - Industries **landfill or incinerate** their waste

Circular model: TERMIT uses **secondary raw materials** from different industries for restoring the mining area.

FIGURE 14: DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE LINEAR AND THE CIRCULAR MODELS IN THE TERMIT CASE

Business Model

Even if the conglomerate works as a consortium, the business model implemented relies on bilateral agreements between individual companies. The business model of the TERMIT symbiosis is presented in the Osterwalder canvas below (Figure 15).

<p>Key Partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ TERMIT ○ HARSCO MINERAL, ○ VIPAP VIDEM ○ KRŠKO ○ CIMOS ○ JUB ○ ABRASIV ○ MUTA ○ KNAUF ISOLATION ○ PETROL ○ STEKLARNA HRASNIK ○ STEKLARNA ROGAŠKA ○ ETI ○ ELEKTROELEMENT ○ LIVAR ○ KOLPA ○ TOPLARNA LJUBLJANA 	<p>Key Activities</p> <p>Waste recycling and production of SRM based construction products for reclamation of degraded mining area</p>	<p>Value Propositions</p> <p>Sustainable resource exploitation, 100% recycled based construction products and sustainable reclamation of degraded mining areas</p>	<p>Customer Relationships</p> <p>B2B:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Supplying wastes to producer for production of SRM based construction products for final use in degraded mining areas ○ Taking over wastes for lower price 	<p>Customer Segments</p> <p>B2B:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Companies increasing their sustainability ○ Increased awareness about SRM based construction products
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collection and separation of wastes ○ Transport of waste ○ Acquiring permits and approvals ○ Recycling ○ Workforce ○ Equipment for recycling and machinery for installation ○ Factory production control ○ Installation 	<p>Key Resources</p> <p>Different industrial wastes SRM based products TERMIT's Recycling facility</p>		<p>Channel</p> <p>B2B bilateral agreements</p>	
	<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collection and separation of wastes ○ Transport of waste ○ Acquiring permits and approvals ○ Recycling ○ Workforce ○ Equipment for recycling and machinery for installation ○ Factory production control ○ Installation 		<p>Revenue Stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Taking over wastes ○ Savings since TERMIT don't need to buy virgin materials 	

FIGURE 15: TERMIT BUSINESS MODEL

Benefits and Risks

This circular model produces different types of benefits. **Environmental benefit** first, as waste are used to produce SRM instead of being landfilled or incinerated. Besides, this model prevents the TERMIT company to use new raw materials in order to achieve the restoration of its mining areas. As illustrated in Table 10, this partnership resulted in tremendous savings for the community and participating companies. The annual material savings total approximately 220,000 tonnes of natural aggregate or soil and almost the same value of saving landfilling place.

Amount of production of SRM based production	Quantity (t)
Tersan	108434
Tersan P	30781
Tersan Ž	28846
Tersan TR	1217
Tersan VRT	30005
Tersan S	395
Harminit	13159
Tersan ETA	784
Tersan SIP	2786
Tersan Jedro	115
TOTAL	216 522

TABLE 10: ANNUAL PRODUCTION OF SRM BASED CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS INBUILT AT TERMIT

Furthermore, the TERMIT Symbiosis engenders also **economic benefits**. Indeed, companies involved in the symbiosis realize a profit when give their waste to TERMIT at a lower price than landfilling or incineration.

One of the major risks identified is the **opposition from the civil society**. For years, a strong opposition led by members of civil society spread rumours on how the company deposited waste in its vicinity. Despite many debates and proofs provided by independent institutions, the opposition is still strong today. This is similar in other such business cases. To solve this issue, the company engaged a dialogue with community through workshops and debates.

Best practices

Several innovation challenges were overcome during the setup of this circular economy model. The most promising one is linked to the **development of new tailored composites made from a large set of waste**. The design of these materials was the result of a strong collaboration between the TERMIT company and ZAG. The company tested the compliance of the product designed according to different scenario of use while ZAG was responsible for getting the Slovenian Technical Approvals.

The main barrier to the TERMIT case was the **low sustainable awareness and acceptance of the model by the local community**. It forced TERMIT to stop its mining recovery with SRM product during a while. One lesson learned could be to **establish a good dialogue with local community** to increase awareness of positive effects of the project. Furthermore, this could lead to increased self-empowerment and develop awareness about sustainability. New green practises such as municipal waste recycling or water restoration may appear. This best practice must be kept in mind when developing the circular cases during PaperChain.

The **main drivers of the model are economic and environmental**. Instead of buying large quantities of new raw materials for restoration of a degraded mining area, the company uses recycled wastes. This model enables the TERMIT company to increase its competitiveness, its growth, creating potential new jobs. In the long-term, environmental benefits are realized through the preservation of new materials and the prevention of landfilling.

The main lesson learned from the TERMIT case is that such circular model can be a solution on multiple levels: technical, technological, environmental, economic and legal. The synergy of the companies in the area has many positive effects and benefits to the whole region. It is also a good example that illustrates how small and medium enterprises can increase their competitiveness. Additionally, new industrial symbiosis networks were created around TERMIT. Companies which used to provide waste are now moving up the value chain, becoming producer of new construction products (replication of the model). In these ways, partners in the TERMIT business case **develop new skills** while the industrial symbiosis network is growing day by day.

3.3. The Thread Company

Context

Thread transforms post-consumer plastic wastes from the streets and canals in Haiti and Honduras into “dignified jobs” and sustainable products to tackle overconsumption, poverty and environmental issues.

Fast fashion is a model developed by apparel retailers in 1990s to provide consumers with clothing collections based on the most recent fashion trends at a low cost. It completely transformed the supply and demand of the apparel industry (Wang 2010). Fed by globalization, the Internet and technological innovation, fast fashion amplified the turnaround of clothing and halved its life cycle in the last decades. “Today’s trends are tomorrow trash” (Madeleine Cobbing & Yannick Vicaire 2016).

Fast fashion occurs at the expense of environment. This intense consumption worsens the ecological footprint of an industry that was already considered, “one of the most polluting in the world” (Muthu 2014). Although the environmental impact of textiles depends on the original fibre source, it generally includes:

- Soil contamination due to chemicals (fertilisers, pesticides and herbicides) released during the production of fibre crops
- Greenhouse gas emissions related to the large amount of energy used during the washing and dyeing processes of fabrication. As an illustration, the purchase and use of clothing accounts for 850MtCO_{2eq}, namely 3% of global CO₂ emission (Carbon Trust 2011)
- The extensive water consumption required in cotton crop cultivation

The environmental damage of the textile industry is not limited to the “fabrication” and “use” steps of the clothing life cycle, but also encompasses its end of life waste streams. Worldwide, tons of clothes end up either landfilled or incinerated: “more than 15 million (tons) of used textile waste is generated each year in the US and the amount has doubled over the last 20 years” (Rick Leblanc 2017) while almost 100% of textiles and clothing are recyclable.

Thread is a certified B corporation, meaning that the company meets certain social sustainability, governance and environmental performance standards. **Thread transforms post-consumer wastes from the streets and canals in Haiti and Honduras into “dignified jobs” and sustainable products.**

FIGURE 16: THREAD DESIGN WORKSHOP (THREAD INTERNATIONAL, 2017)

In 2016, Thread collected more than 148 tons of plastic waste from the poorest neighbourhoods in Haiti and Honduras. The fibre and yarn produced from these plastics are the final products in Thread's circular model, which fed the fabrication processes of 351 customers, generating a revenue totalling \$743,381 in 2016 (Thread 2016). Furthermore, Thread brings “economic opportunity and advancement to bottom of the pyramid populations, while cleaning streets and improving communities” (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2017). This company, founded in the wake of the Haiti earthquake in 2010, allows low-income countries to invest directly into innovative waste management and the circular economy. Thread accelerates an industrial leapfrog with high environmental and social benefits in these countries.

System

Transparency is at the heart of Thread, which relies on an interactive platform to trace the path of all plastic goods collected and transformed by its employees. Figure 17 summarises Thread organisation and represents the different flows between the stakeholders. Thread process begins in Haiti streets where 1,300 people participate in the Ramase Lajan Program, an initiative that allows locals to collect plastic in exchange for cash. The collected plastic is sold to 26 collection centres owned and operated by the local population before being washed and sorted out by ECSSA, a local environmental specialist organisation that transforms the plastic waste into usable flakes. After being shipped to US facilities, the flakes undergo melting and extrusion processes to be transformed successively into fibre and fabric. This end-product is sold to be cut and sewn into customer product as new raw material (Thread 2013). The whole process is illustrated in Figure 18.

FIGURE 17: THREAD ORGANISATION

Thread and the international outdoor lifestyle company, Timberland, started a partnership in June 2016. Timberland is developing sustainable operational procedures and seeks to guarantee its pioneering status in the circular economy by integrating the recycled fibre in its new line of goods. The 2017 line of Timberland shoes and bags will be made of recycled PET sourced from plastic bottles.

FIGURE 18: COMPARISON OF LINEAR AND CIRCULAR MODEL OF TEE SHIRT

Business Model

Thread business model is based on an approach that builds value for both the environment and the people. Although the Osterwalder canvas is probably not appropriate to represent the social and environmental benefit create by the company, it gives an idea on how the company prosper economically (Figure 19).

<u>Key Partners</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Member of the Ramase Laja program Network of trash collection center Processing company (ECSSA) 	<u>Key Activities</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect plastic trash Transform trash into flakes Process flakes into fabric Sell yarn and clothes 	<u>Value Propositions</u> <i>Thread international transforms trashes into dignified incomes and responsible outcomes</i>	<u>Customer Relationships</u> <u>B2C</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivery of Thread goods Publicity for partners' template made with Thread goods Circular model: consumers send products back to Thread when they are finished. <u>B2B</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delivery of Thread goods 	<u>Customer Segments</u> <u>B2C</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proactive consumers informed about sustainable development and circular economy <u>B2B</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies that give attention to their environmental footprint
	<u>Key Resources</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plastic trash Fabric facilities 		<u>Channel</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web communication Blog Partnership with social organizations (Clinton Global Initiative) 	
<u>Cost Structure</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collection of trashes Transformation activities Shipping Fabric facilities Workforce Creation and maintenance of the website 			<u>Revenue Stream</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partnerships with clothing manufacturers Sell of goods to consumers 	

FIGURE 19: THREAD BUSINESS MODEL

Benefits and risks

In 2016, Thread carried out a Life Cycle Analysis on the Timberland goods made of recycled plastic. Compared to usual 100% cotton canvas produced, the Thread "Ground to Good Canvas" is 6% less carbon intensive and consumes less water by a factor of 41. Moreover, apparels with a lower percentage of cotton inputs imply a reduction in total fertiliser and herbicide consumption.

The circular economic model implemented by Thread helps developing countries to reduce their environmental footprint. In 2016, 17 tons of plastics were collected in the streets of Haiti and Honduras (Thread 2016). Thread's waste recycling initiative also generates health benefits. According to Ian Rosenberger, founder and CEO of Thread, "poor countries tend to be the most vulnerable when it comes to waste infrastructure", which is a breeding ground for epidemics. The reduction of compounding waste streams can significantly improve public health in developing countries. In addition to the positive environmental and social impacts, the company also improves the local economy (Table 11). In 2015, the partnership created 287 jobs in low-incomes countries, which generated \$124,098 in revenue (Thread 2016). Furthermore, Thread makes a difference by its **social impact**. The job is initially given to women. In 2016, 46% of employees in the working across supply chains were women. The company developed also an initiative that addresses child labour in plastic collection. The initiative consists in providing adolescents working in plastic collection with access to healthcare, safety equipment and sanitation training, educational scholarships, jobs training and mentorship.

Thread's business models are threatened by three main risks: child labour, supply risks, and scalability. The **child labour** risks have been identified and treated as illustrated by the child

labour initiative. Given the amount of plastic in the street of Honduras and Haiti, the **lack of supply** is a very limited risk. However, **quality control** could really pose a risk to the plastic flake supply chain if not properly enforced. The third pitfall concerns the **scalability** of Thread's solution. Without partners such as Timberland and ECSSA, the impact of Thread may be limited. Recently, studies have questioned the **environmental benefit** of using recycled plastic waste. (Mark Browne et al 2011) asserts that the recycled plastic might end up in oceans anyway, under a "soup" state that is even worse for the environment.

Benefits (2016)	
Job creation in Haiti	233
Revenue of plastic waste exported	\$91,987
Tons of plastics exported	148
Professional development and training	1,046 hours

TABLE 11: THREAD BENEFITS IN 2016

Best Practices

Thread is a working example of a company succeeding in combining a circular and **social impact dimension** into its business model. The **economic and environmental improvements** achieved by the company were also possible because of the importance given to the "first mile" of the supply chain. The mind-set and the values of the company illustrated by their slogan "it's about the people, people" were certainly key for Thread's success. The generation of economic revenue is vital for a company, but other form of income, such as social value, could contribute to the global success of a company. In addition of this first best practise, PaperChain partners could be inspired by the importance given to all the stakeholders along the supply chain, particularly the ones at the bottom of the pyramid. Finally, Thread's example brings the importance of **partnership** into light. Built partnerships among PaperChain partners could give life to new circular and virtuous cycles.

In a nutshell, the key to Thread's success is the **involvement of the local population** in creating a solution for the most environmental, economic and social benefits. **Built partnerships with international companies** like Timberland and HP, which share the same values, are also a catalyst. A final parameter that can explain Thread success is the **low-cost nature of the infrastructure** required for its business.

3.4. The Weber example

Context

Within the Cluster Sustainable Habitat strategy, Saint-Gobain Weber, The Navigator Company, University of Aveiro and RAIZ worked together to develop an adhesive mortar (reference WEBER.col flex L).

The mortar is used for bonding ceramic, natural stone and large and medium format hydraulic mosaic on exterior and interior facades, floors and walls. It is currently on the market and commercialised by Saint-Gobain.

System

This circular case is an example of industrial symbiosis between two relevant PaperChain sectors, namely the Pulp and Paper Industry and the Construction sector. Indeed, the Navigator Company provides **aggregates (sand) from the fluidized bed of biomass boilers**. **Saint Gobain uses this waste after improvement to replace natural raw material in a mortar contributing so for the efficient use of resources.**

To carry on with this construction material solution and implement it in the market, a third **industrial stakeholder was required to take care of the waste transference and upgrade it so that it can be used in the mortar formulation**. During the R&D stage, tests were already conducted with a SME (SACT) that was specialized in aggregates washing and sieving.

The role of each partner is explained in Figure 20:

FIGURE 20: THE WEBER EXAMPLE

Business Model

The business model for Saint Gobain is presented on the figure below, using the Osterwalder canvas:

<u>Key Partners</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Waste manager The navigator Company Raiz UAVR 	<u>Key Activities</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Producing the Weber mortar Commercialising the mortar 	<u>Value Proposition</u> <i>Mortar used for bonding ceramic, natural stone and large and medium format hydraulic mosaic based on aggregates from the PPI</i>	<u>Customer Relationships</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relying on one of the leaders of the construction materials industry 	<u>Customer Segments</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction companies Distributors
	<u>Key Resources</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> R&D Production lines Legal permit to use aggregates 		<u>Channel</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web communication Distribution via distributors network 	
<u>Cost Structure</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw materials Aggregates Distribution of the mortar workforce 			<u>Revenue Stream</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revenues from the sales of the Weber mortar 	

FIGURE 21: SAINT-GOBAIN'S BUSINESS MODEL FOR THE WEBER EXAMPLE

Benefits and Risks

Since the beginning of this partnership in 2015, there is about 900 tons per year of aggregates (75 tons per month) being sent to the SME company responsible for washing and sieving the waste sand. From the 900 tons of waste about 60% is sent to the mortar company and the rest is used on other applications. After this treatment, it can be directly used as a replacement of natural raw material (sand) in the St. Gobain-Weber mortar factory. **Saint Gobain manages to save around 540 tons of natural sand every year with a reduced cost.**

The Navigator Company saved the landfill costs of its waste. The cost for landfill for this particular material is around 7.7€/ton which meaning that a **7000€ saving is generated every year by the PPI plant.**

Finally, the SME company responsible for the waste **management gained a new business and 2 new clients.** This example of **circular case is a 3-way win-win situation.**

During the final stage of this case the most difficult barrier appeared to **be the legal constraints in the public sector.** After solving the technical problem during 1 year, it took almost one year and a half to get the public permit to carry on the operation legally.

Best practices

From the Weber example, two main best practices can be identified. First, it is important to involve the waste manager from the beginning of the project, to avoid technical or supply problems. Then, project managers should start as soon as possible the legal process to obtain the required permits, since it can take some time.

3.5. The ELM example

Context

Nowadays, urban and landfill mining is becoming trendy alternatives for confronting waste problems in our society: stimulating sustainable production and consumption, decreasing GHG emissions and increasing recycling, resource recovery and efficiency between other grand global social, economic and environmental challenges. In this context, Enhanced Landfill Mining concept (ELFM) is one of the clearest examples of contemporary circular economy business models, **aiming at converting present landfills into reusable raw materials and energy**. Other approaches based on landfill mining exist besides ELFM, such as Enhanced bioreactor or Sustainable landfills.

ELFM is defined as “the safe exploration, conditioning, excavation and integrated valorisation of (historic, present and/or future) landfilled waste streams as both materials (Waste-to-Material, WtM) and energy (Waste-to-Energy, WtE), using innovative transformation technologies and respecting the most stringent social and ecological criteria.” (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2012.05.021>).

One of the most relevant ELFM projects is The Closing the Circle (CtC) project at the landfill of Remo in Houthalen-Helchteren (Belgium). It is estimated that this landfill contains more than 16 million tonnes of household and commercial wastes. Other estimations report that about 45% of the waste could be recycled into materials and that the rest has enough potential caloric value to be used for energy generation after pertinent pre-treatments.

The CtC project is led by the Flemish ELFM Consortium and will take about 20 years in total to valorise all the stored waste and transform the landfill into a nature park. The Consortium is formed by academic experts in several disciplines, the private company Group Machiels, the Flemish Public Waste Agency (OVAM) and some representatives of the local communities.

The CtC project is being developed in several phases. From 2007 to 2008 the concept phase was developed. From 2008 to 2012, valorisation tests and detail engineering were performed to develop a pilot scale project up to 2017. Onwards, the plants enabling WtE (Plasma Demonstration Plant) and WtM will be built for an industrial scale phase and validate the ELFM concept.

To achieve these goals, technical innovations have been developed in a continuous way from the early stages. The CtC project began envisaging the use of gas engines or gas turbines to produce energy and heat from syngas (produced by the plasma gasification processes). Last version of the project included hydrogen, natural gas or liquid fuels from the produced syngas, which enhances the sustainable potential of the project.

The whole CtC project requires funds for about 240M€ and estimations are about 800 employments plus other 200 from indirect employments. From then on, some other expected innovations can reach the market, such as new services to other landfills, new technologies and new processes, besides new business models.

Thereafter the concept phase, a European network was created under the name of EURELCO, supporting the required technological, legal, social, economic, environmental and organisational innovations about Enhanced Landfill Mining.

EURELCO is leading EU funded landfill mining projects, nationally/regionally funded landfill mining projects, bilateral & consultancy landfill mining projects and other kind of projects.

System

It is very difficult to identify the role of each contributor since it is an ongoing project. Nevertheless, the different steps of the valorisation of waste into materials or energy can be further described. First, **assessments of waste** were realised to verify the quantity and their characterization by dividing wastes in different categories, according to the registrations. Some assumptions about degradation of the wastes (textile, paper, cardboard and organic fraction) were also realised and resulted in an intermediate estimation of 13 million metric tons of dry waste in Remo landfill in different categories, such as industrial wastes (about 5 million tons) and MSW from households and companies (about 7,5 million tons).

Field tests were then carried out in order to validate the quality of the wastes and check the change in composition of the wastes ensuing from their long storage. These data are essential to valorise the potential of the landfill and confirm that the composition and characteristics of the material were modified along the time. Besides, these tests were useful to correct the first assumption about degradation of the wastes and to valorise the real potential of the landfill into secondary raw materials and into energy. Onwards, a separation plant was designed and tested to produce combustible fraction and material recycling, it will be incorporated soon into the industrial scale plant.

Pilot tests were carried out to assess the theoretical efficiencies. Net electrical efficiency of 20% and 23% validate the stability of the process.

From then on, **a Plasma Demonstration Installation (Figure 22), as a part of the CtC industrial Consortium will be developed from 2017 to 2021**. Each industrial member of this Consortium will be in charge of the different EPC (Engineering-Procurement-Construction) subsystems inside the whole plant.

FIGURE 22: GASPLASMA CYCLE

Figure 23 represents different studied according from their environmental, social and economic impacts. From top to bottom is illustrated increasingly ambitious scenario from “doing nothing” scenario to the ELMF concept.

FIGURE 23: THE DIFFERENT SCENARIOS FOR THE VALORISATION OF WASTE IN THE ELMF EXAMPLE

Business model

The Flemish EFLM Consortium was built to support the design and the development of required installations for the Plasma Demo Installation of the Remo landfill project. The business model (Figure 24) the consortium as a whole is first of all to demonstrate the potential approach at Remo landfill in a technical, environmental, social and economical way.

<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Local communities o EURELCO o Flemish authority o Universities and academic experts o Group Machiels 	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Analysis of landfill in theoretical/testing o Valorisation of wastes o Fuel preparation and material separation o Geoplasma plant EPC o Sell Energy, Heat and Fuels o Sell secondary raw materials 	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <p>CtC project transform wastes into energy and secondary raw materials (WtE, WtM)</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u></p> <p>Publicity on secondary raw materials based on circular economy models</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Public Green Procurement Directives for authority o Construction companies interested in recycled materials o Greenhouses for botaingn heat at a good price o Agricultural sector for cheap and rich fertilizers o Companies for renewable energy
<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Wastes from households and companies</p>		<p><u>Channel</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Web and blog o Workshops for local communities o TV and radio 		
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Transformation plants o Plasma installation plant o Temporary storage 			<p><u>Revenue Stream</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Build installations in other landfills o Sell services as valorisation consulting o Selling energy to net o Selling heat and fuels o Selling secondary raw materials 	

FIGURE 24: BUSINESS MODEL FOR THE EFLM EXAMPLE

Besides, the business model will realize benefits for **selling energy, heat and fuel** to local companies and neighbourhoods.

A second source of income is linked to the **selling of raw materials** for different sectors such as fertilizers, gravels, cement, etc.

One longer-term objective of the Consortium is to **replicate the technical solutions developed in a worldwide perspective**, not only for selling the design and construction of plasma installations, but selling services for valorisation of current landfills.

The potential for replication is huge. According to EURELCO more than 500,000 landfills containing 80% of basically Urban Solid Waste and 20% of specific industrial wastes exist all over Europe.

Benefits and risks

First estimations made by CtC about the key figures about the impact of ELFM on EU level highlights that about **150.000-500.000 landfills as potential markets with more than 5.000 million tons of waste**. These wastes could be potentially transformed in 7 million tonnes of oil equivalent (TOE) and help to achieve environmental objectives producing 3% of European renewable energy targets at 2020 and decreasing CO₂ emissions by 8 million tons a year.

The benefits of the CtC project on the environment are numerous:

- Decrease CO₂ emissions
- Provide fertilizers for local agriculture
- Produce heat and clean energy
- Avoid the use of fossil fuels
- Save energy from WtM, restoring landfills into nature parks,
- Produce cement for construction and some other secondary raw materials.

The benefits on social and economics are the creation of direct employments (0.8 million of direct jobs), and restoration of landfills into parks.

The project contains risks. It is possible to point out the **heterogeneity and lack of knowledge of the wastes disposed on landfills**. Consequently, the real potential of landfilled waste is uncertain so far. The replication of such system requires a proper inventory and quality tests of wastes. Besides, it depends strongly on the cultural heritage about recycling and the disposal of social community and industrial organisations.

Another non-technical barrier is that the **temporary storage** needed on ELFM projects are not suitable with the European Waste Framework (2008/98/EC) and Landfill (99/31/EC) directives, that limits them to three years. This implies that the storage of waste in ELFM landfills needs to be considered as disposal if it is storage longer than three years. The legal framework for temporary landfills should be then adjusted.

Besides, ELFM projects might cause noise, light and visual disturbance on ecosystems and in neighbourhoods.

Finally regarding economics, the cost-effectiveness of these project is difficult to reach without the help of public fund.

Lessons learned

The PAPERCHAIN project can obtain a better understanding about best practices applied in CtC. It could result in **new processes to obtain secondary raw materials and energy generation in a sustainable** and circular economy way of acting. Consequently, one of the most important best practices is identified as making a Life Cycle Assessment and a Life Cost Cycle (LCA/LCC). Such practise could help to imagine a second lease of life.

Besides, it is mandatory to make a continuous technological innovation in PAPERCHAIN in order to reduce costs along the value chain. Due to the great amount of funds and the transversal disciplines required, such ambitious project could be only carried out by a strong industrial Consortium formed by technological, scientific, academic and industrial partners.

Other main point focus should be the **legal barriers** from the European Waste Framework. Adjustments are necessary in order to reuse the secondary raw materials obtained through PAPERCHAIN from wastes into the market and enable the storage of waste over long periods of time.

Besides, making an **international network** will help to decrease or eliminate non-technical barriers about treatment of wastes from European Waste Directives.

4. Description and analysis of paperchain circular cases

As explained in the Introduction chapter (see Figure 2), an explorative process of pilot cases that constitute the demonstration step in PAPERCHAIN project will be developed along the whole WP3. The first iteration of such a process is presented in this section. For each demo case, the context is described as well as the stakeholders involved are represented on a value chain. Finally, the expected benefits and challenges that were identified at proposal stage have been updated.

This first iteration when exploring the PAPERCHAIN demo cases will allow the partners to set up the basis for a generic characterisation of the circular economy models they represent during task 3.2.

FIGURE 25: MAP OF THE DIFFERENT CIRCULAR CASES IN PAPERCHAIN

4.1. Circular case 1: PPI and the construction manufacturing sector in Portugal

Presentation of the Demo case

The proposed circular model is a resource efficiency partnership in Portugal involving a paper and pulp industry (PPI), and companies from the construction sector in a clear example of industrial symbiosis.

Dregs and grits (PPI wastes) will be valorised as alternative raw materials incorporated in a bituminous mixture for the construction of a road stretch (≈250 m) in Portugal. Simultaneously, another PPI waste, lime mud, will be processed to replace natural limestone fillers in precast concrete. Waste containing concrete will be produced for precast concrete manufacturing and a portico structural unit will be built for the project.

The principle of the circular case 1 is presented Figure 26

FIGURE 26: MAIN PRINCIPLE OF CIRCULAR CASE 1

The circular mode 1 upgrades PPI particulate waste into alternative or secondary raw materials that replace traditional virgin raw material feed stocks in the production of precast concrete for construction projects or bituminous mixtures for road construction.

Stakeholders & value chain

The concept will be demonstrated by improving the wastes quality at the Navigator plant and by carrying out two technical pilot demonstrators at the location managed by SPRAL and MEGAVIA: a trial with two precast concrete structures (SCC) produced for a set of porticos and an asphalt road stretch.

FIGURE 27: TWO DEMO PILOTS FOR THE CIRCULAR CASE 1 IN PORTUGAL

The four main stakeholders in this Circular Case demo are all located close to each other. The first is **THE NAVIGATOR COMPANY**, a paper and pulp industry that will provide, if needed, waste improvements (DREGS, GRITS and LIME MUD) to upgrade their quality as a potential raw material. They will collaborate on the technical support needed for the legal and environmental provisions required for market uptake.

The second stakeholder, **SPRAL**, is a precast concrete producer, responsible for the demo's execution of concrete based solutions. They will contribute to the modifications required at the concrete plant for the incorporation of the PPI waste (Lime mud). They will execute the field trial and monitoring process to ensure environmental and mechanical performance.

The third stakeholder, **MEGAVIA**, is a construction company devoted to road and pavement projects, and is responsible for the adoption of asphalt pavement based solutions. They will contribute to the execution of all on site modifications needed to enable the use of PPI wastes (DREGS and GRITS) in the field trial, and they will monitor the project's environmental and technical performance.

Finally, the University of Aveiro **UAVR** will oversee the whole implementation of the circular case.

The role of each partner is represented in Figure 28

FIGURE 28: STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN THE CIRCULAR CASE 1

The Navigator Company operates four mills in Portugal (Cacia, Figueira da Foz, Setúbal and Vila Velha do Ródão), which have an annual production capacity of 1.6 million tons of paper and 1.4 million tons of pulp, of which 1.1 million tonnes can be integrated. The chemical recovery cycle for the kraft pulping process in the Cacia mill generates, per year, 4,500 tonnes of Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) and Grits (32,000 tonnes for total NVG mills) and 2,800 tonnes of lime mud waste (20,000 tonnes for total NVG mills), which are mainly disposed of in controlled landfills. Each year several kilometres of roads are built or repaired, and many other residential, industrial or construction projects are initiated. The project can be replicated in another PPI plants inside and outside Portugal. MEGAVIA and SPRAL are two different construction companies that have several on-going construction projects that can easily replicate the proposed circular case.

Benefits and Challenges

There are substantial economic and ecological benefits in adopting circular economic models for construction projects. Although there are some challenges, they can easily be overcome to accelerate the transition from the linear model to the circular model.

The Navigator Company has carried out R&D in the past years with the University of Aveiro (UAVR) to exploit valuable uses for inorganic industrial wastes. Nowadays, dregs, grits and lime mud are the most difficult to value and deserve special attention. Previous research by NAV and UAVR has shown that it is possible to incorporate them in several construction materials, replacing aggregates or fillers without hindering their final properties. This will

result in environmental and economic benefits due to the reduction of landfill disposal and the savings stemming from natural raw material displacement.

For the pilot demo in Portugal, the estimated amount of recycled waste into product is about 3 tons of lime mud, 19 tons of Dregs and 32 tons of Grits. Moreover, the estimated by-product replacement of natural raw materials (aggregates and fillers) will lead to 43 tons of natural raw materials savings. The amount of savings in the following 2 years of the project can ascend to 40,000 tonnes of lime mud, and 65,000 tonnes of Dregs and Grits. After the project period, the savings of natural raw materials are around 100,000 tonnes. Clearly this represents a significant environmental, social and economic impact. It is important for these demos to confirm their impact after project, so that a business model based on a win-win situation can arise from the competitive nature of the solution and the project's needs, a third party will bridge the waste generator (PPI) and the solution provider (construction sector). The dynamic of this partner will be between a waste manager and an extractive industry expert.

Benefit	Quantification	Actor
Avoided landfill fees for NVG (3 mills)	300,000€	The Navigator Company
Dregs and grits recycled as eco-bitumen (3 mills)	32,000 tons	The Navigator Company and Megavia
Lime mud recycled as eco-concrete (3mills)	20,000 tons	The Navigator Company and SPRAL

TABLE 12: ANNUAL SYMBIOSIS BENEFITS

4.2. Circular case 2: PPI and the railway sector in Spain

Presentation of the Demo case

The circular case 2 represents an example of Resource Recovery circular model. It aims at the valorisation of ash produced by SAICA (a Spanish recycling pulp mill) as alternative binder for soil stabilization works in road projects (Spanish roads).

The circular case 2 represents an example of Resource Recovery circular model. It aims at the valorisation of ash produced in the energy recovery from paper waste produced by SAICA (a Spanish recycling pulp mill) as alternative binder for soil stabilization works in road projects. SAICA operates an energy valorisation plant that burns sludge paper waste produced in four of their paper mills to generate 49 MWhe. As a consequence, 55,000 tonnes of fly ash and bottom ash are produced every year, being all of them disposed to landfill.

During last years, ACCIONA (Spanish waste manager) in collaboration with SAICA and the Regional transportation authority have been conducting research on the valorisation of PPI wastepaper ash for construction. Previous results at laboratory and small scale field trials show that waste paper ash (WPA) can act as binding agent in soil stabilization for subgrade applications, subbase layers (soil-cement) and pavement recycling.

The energy valorisation plant is located in the municipality of El Burgo de Ebro (Zaragoza), a relevant agricultural area with an extended network of country roads which demand a lot of expenditures in maintenance works. Nowadays, many of them remain in poor condition. Moreover, this region is planning to built more than 150 km of highways in the coming years.

The proposed alternative is a circular renewability and recycling model for the production of new binders in three pilot cases, from the less complex and easier to reach the market (country roads), to the most complex and regulated ones (highways) after demonstrating its technical and environmental performance.

The principle of the circular case 2 is presented Figure 29.

FIGURE 29 – CIRCULAR PROPOSAL FOR BINDERS PRODUCTION (SOIL STABILIZATION)

Stakeholders & Value Chain

As mentioned above, the main stakeholders in Circular Case 2 are located in Spain representing the pulp and paper industry: **SAICA**; the waste manager: **ACCIONA**, a large construction company which will be in charge of the adaptations of current construction procedures to the alternative binders; the technical support provided by **UPC**: a Spanish university providing technical support for dimensioning, structural calculation, modelling, testing and monitoring. Additionally, three Spanish Public Authorities will participate: Municipality of El Burgo de Ebro, Government of Aragón and Spanish Ministry of Transportation in charge of supporting the demonstration activities and potential adopters of the new product resulting from the circular model.

- **Burgo de Ebro Municipality:** Spanish municipality that will provide 1 km long country road to implement the demonstration activity.
- **Spanish Ministry of Public Works:** Spanish public authority that will support the Spanish demonstrator activities at national level.
- **General Roads Directorate of Aragón province:** Spanish public authority that will be interested in project results and will support the Spanish demonstrator activities at regional level.

The role of each partner is represented in FIGURE 30.

FIGURE 30 – STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN THE CIRCULAR CASE 2

SAICA was founded over 70 years ago, but remains a family owned business, which is a market leader in Spain that produces sustainable solutions for paper and board packaging. They are present in the integrated paper cycle as the Figure 31 shows.

FIGURE 31 – SAICA IN PAPER CYCLE (SOURCE: [HTTP://WWW.SAICA.COM/EN/WHOAREWE/PAGES/WHOAREWE.ASPX](http://www.saica.com/en/whoarewe/pages/whoarewe.aspx))

SAICA applies a circular business strategy across all of its divisions. The division that participates in PAPERCHAIN, Saica Natur, strives for Zero Waste, always seeking ways to recover paper, cardboard, plastic and organic waste, among others, and designing the most effective solutions possible for their reuse and conversion to value (SAICA 2016). SAICA which will provide the required waste amounts for the demos. The three pilots will lead to the valorisation of 90 tonnes of fly ash in the country road, 190 tonnes of fly ash by using 6.5 % of ashes instead of cement in the S-EST3 field trial and 120 tonnes of bottom ashes replacing 7 % of volume in cement in the soil-cement layer.

Benefits and Challenges

There are substantial **economic and ecological benefits** in adopting this Resource Recovery circular model of recovering ash as alternative binder for soil stabilization works in road projects. Previous research has been developed in this field.

Ground granulated blast furnace slag and class C fly ash have been used in soil stabilization in USA and Australia (Roads and Maritime Services 2011). In Europe, the use of ashes can be also considered under the European standard UNE-14227, though its market uptake for roads still is being reduced. As waste paper ash gained in relevance, researchers have paid attention to this option, finding valuable its composition to replace cement in concrete and soil stabilisation (Segui, et al. 2012), due to the presence of cementitious minerals and pozzolanic phases, such as metakaolin, calcium aluminates and silicates and free lime. Small scale field trials have been performed confirming its applicability (Vega et Romero 2015). In addition, the government of the UK pre-assessed WPA as useful and non-harmful for the environment (Marstrand & Whiteley 2015). Dutch company CDEM Minerals (CDEM s.d.) produces ashes as additive for concrete and soil stabilisation, burning deinking paper sludge from three mills at the optimal temperature for

the highest quality. Additionally, a new standard about hydraulic road binders (HRBs) was published in 2016 (EN-13282-2, normal hardening HRBs). This standard included ashes from paper sludge as a potential component for HRBs, although limiting it up to 40 % of the total mix.

Although there are some challenges that need to be addressed to guarantee the transition from the linear model. EN-13282-2 was not cited in the OJEU and now is under revision due to discrepancies about this limit and the needed pre-treatments for testing. In spite of these experiences and standardization trials with the sludge ash, there is a **lack of knowledge and experience with wastepaper ash** (WPA) coming with the energy valorisation of paper rejects and mixtures of sludge and rejects. Nowadays almost all WPA is disposed to landfills due to the **existing legal barriers and a lack of knowledge** at both, regulator and construction company levels. Regulators are reluctant to approve WPA due to the lack of knowledge about its environmental behaviour in real environments as well as its technical performance over the long term in road projects. **Key durability aspects** such as fatigue strength and freeze-thaw resistance must be demonstrated, as well as the **evolution of mechanical parameters**, such as compressive strength and Young's modulus, to establish a correlation between cement and WPA, required for road section dimensioning. Moreover, construction companies are reluctant to change well-established materials such as cement or quicklime due to any change which might lead to a lower productivity in operational procedures or problems with soil stabilisers designed to use cement or quicklime.

In terms of market expectations, taking into account that the market for asphalt is not country-specific around Europe, to be economically viable, **customers for PPI waste must be located close to the PPI to avoid high transport costs**. In addition, once asphalt is produced, the distance of transport is limited, as asphalt must be delivered to the paving site while it is still warm enough to be placed and compacted. In terms of the market size and replication potential, in Europe, around 90 % of the 5.2 million km of paved roads and highways are surfaced with asphalt. At European level, there are about 4700 asphalt production sites (EAPA s.d.), in 2012. This implies an average demand of 275 million tons of asphalt pavement material.

There are several barriers with significant impact that have been identified so far: **Licensing and legal authorization, Waste regulation, Lack of standards, Internal Reluctance to introduce changes, Public perception, Price and Environmental impact**.

The intensive use of cement in subgrade layers represents 30% of the total costs of a stabilised layer. An estimated amount of 400.000 tonnes is produced in Europe yearly. Moreover, 150 Kms of highways are projected for the following years solely in the influence area of the demonstrator, which implies a necessity of more than 100.000 tonnes of cement for the main cement-modified layers. The use of WPA could contribute to diminish economic and environmental costs of using cement and quicklime.

As a consequence of the project, 90 tonnes of fly ash will be valorised in the country road. 190 tonnes of fly ash by using 6.5 % of ashes instead of cement in the S-EST3 field trial and 120 tonnes of bottom ashes by adding a 7 % instead of cement in the soil-cement layer, which represents savings of 300.000 € and 94.4 tonnes of CO₂eq (with respect to CEMIII type). The replication of the model is estimated to reach 700.000 m³ of stabilised soils in

the 2nd scenario, and a potential consumption of 80.000 tonnes of PSA to replace 40.000 tonnes of cement with an economic impact of 9.9 million € including both, cement savings and landfill fees, as well as the avoidance of 19.100 tonnes of GHG emissions. All mentioned benefits are summarized in the table below (Table 13).

<i>Benefit</i>	<i>Quantification</i>	<i>Actor</i>
Valorised Fly ash	90 tonnes (at country level)	SAICA
CO2 emission prevention	94.4 tonnes	All actors
Economic Savings	300.000 €	Stabilizing agent
Cement savings and landfill fees	9.9 million €	

Table 13: Impacts of the circular case 2

4.3. Circular case 3: PPI and the road sector in Slovenia

Presentation of the Demo case

The circular model 3 is a resource efficiency partnership between the paper industry VIPAP and railway operator Slovenian Railway – Infrastructure to produce a composite material for slope stabilisation.

During the last years, ZAG has been searching to find alternative cost-effective materials based on PPI waste products. Thus, an innovative composite made of Deinking Paper Ash (DPA) and Deinking Paper Sludge (DPS) has been developed. This material has interesting characteristics: it has a considerable strength (2.70 MPa at 28 curing days), it is light (< 1 t/m³) and easy to handle, especially when the space is limited. Usually for construction work only paper ash is used, which has no high freeze/thaw resistance. For the new composite material, the last freeze/thaw tests indicated that the material reaches the criteria for a backfill material and could be used as a new recycled material at a construction site.

Slovenia is a mountainous country with landslides potentially threatening the safety of roads and railways, which has been addressed through costly actions. In general, the Slovenian railway infrastructure, which consists in 1207 km of railway lines, needs to undergo frequent renovations near the precarious regions. Indeed, railway lines are at least 150 years old and urgently need the renovation activities for the further normal operation.

The proposed alternative is a circular renewability and recycling model based on the composite material (proper mix of PSA and DPS) which can be used for slope stabilisation of a railway infrastructure. As shown on Figure 32, the material will replace the natural gravel backfill material.

FIGURE 32 ALTERNATIVE PRODUCTION OF COMPOSITE AND ITS USE FOR SLOPE STABILISATION

The circular demo case in Slovenia will be presented in the southern part of Slovenia. Near the railway line near the city Mirna pec an unstable slope is due for renovation. The 250m long slope is unstable and has visible deformations in the soil, rocks, telephone lines and the road above the slope.

The renovation is planned in two phases, the first one is for the 70 m long PAPERCHAIN project, and the second is based on the results of the first phase in the following years.

FIGURE 33 DEMO SITE IN SLOVENIA

FIGURE 34 UNSTABLE SLOPE EXAMPLE

Stakeholders & value chain

All the stakeholders in the Slovenian Circular Case are partners of the PAPERCHAIN project. The first is a large paper production company, **VIPAP VIDEM KRŠKO** d.d, a producer of newsprint and coated graphic paper. The main raw material is recycled fibre recovered from the paper deinking process. VIPAP's annual output capacity is 240,000 tonnes; i.e.

180,000 tonnes of recycled fibres, and 60,000 tonnes of groundwood pulp. VIPAP will supply ash and paper sludge for the project's research activities and final composite for the demo site. Annually, 25.000 tonnes of ash are produced, most of which are still disposed to landfill.

Slovenian Railways is a wholly state-owned enterprise and the company, SŽ- Infrastructure, provides maintenance and management for public railway infrastructure, rail traffic, and transport of passengers and goods on public railway infrastructure. SŽ will provide a demo site with an identified landslide problem, organize a building site and provide support for the demonstration project's execution.

The **DH Company** was founded in 2010, and specializes in earthwork projects throughout the construction sector. The company is located in Trbovlje, a Slovenian town quite close to the demo site. DH will provide the earthwork for the proposed demo site. The draft plan of the gabion/composite structure is presented in Figure 35.

FIGURE 35 CONSTRUCTION OF THE RETAINING WALL (GABIONS AND COMPOSITE)

The implementation of circular case 3 will be supervised by **ZAG**. The role of each partner involved in this circular case is represented in Figure 36:

FIGURE 36: STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN THE CIRCULAR CASE 3

Benefits and challenges

There are substantial economic, ecological and social benefits in adopting circular economic models for the use of new material composites (PSA+DPS) for slope stabilisation. PAPERCHAIN will demonstrate the use of this recycled composite as a valuable material for the rehabilitation of landslides near roads and railway lines. The recycled material (DPA/DPS) will be installed between the gabions and the wall of the slope instead of virgin - natural gravel material. As the new material has higher strength characteristics, a thinner gabion wall can be used. The use of recycled composites instead of natural gravel will contribute to the preservation of natural resources. The production of gravel material in quarries has a high environmental impact. With the use of the recycled material, **CO2 emissions will be reduced** during both construction and maintenance phases. For the demo purposes, at least 50 tonnes of the DWPA/DPS composite will be used as part of the retaining walls structural solutions, replacing up to 30 % of the gabions and 100 % backfill gravel material.

The project can be easily replicated throughout the Slovenian railway network since the whole value chain is involved in the project's demonstration. Also, Slovenia is a mountainous region with many unaddressed landslide problems near their railway and road infrastructure. **The new method can be replicated** in every country that is threatened by earthy and stone landslides. The potential market is in Austria, Swiss, Italy, France, Spain, Norway and Balkan countries.

The use of waste material, such as the PSA and DPS in composites, diverts significant amounts of waste material from the landfill, which **decreases the cost of disposal** for the pulp and paper company.

Benefit	Quantification	Actor
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CO2 emission prevention for one landslide in the approximate length of 100 m (natural back fill material is not used any more)	9t Co2	All actors
The use of virgin back filling material (gravel material) will decrease (assuming at least 5 landslides stabilisations per year with the Paperchain solution)	650 t	DH
Avoided landfill for paper ash	25.000 t	VIPAP
Avoided landfill fees for paper ash	3.750.000 € savings The price for the paper ash landfill is 150€/t	VIPAP
Increase of the gabions production capacity if the method of the landslide stabilization will be used also for the road infrastructure	10% Increase	SŽ group

TABLE 14: IMPACTS OF THE CIRCULAR CASE 3

Finally, SŽ frequently uses gabions-based retaining walls because one of the SŽ group's companies is a gabion producer. This company has a special status because it employs only disabled persons. The new method for the landslide stabilization will be cheap and simple and it is expected to be implemented not only for railway but also for the road infrastructure. With the increase of use of gabions for railway and road infrastructure and, with the increase of the gabions production, the company could employ more disabled people, which could have **high social impact**.

However, the circular case also presents challenges such as the use of a new material. In the laboratory mixing of the material does not cause any problems, but in the construction site the situation could be completely different. On the construction site, **large quantities of material are required, and must be homogenized**. To avoid this problem few smaller test fields with different mixing procedure will be tested.

4.4. Circular case 4: PPI and the chemical industry in Sweden

Presentation of the Demo case

The proposed circular model is a resource efficiency partnership in an industrial site in Domsjö, Sweden, between the sulphite mill Domsjö Fabriker and chemical plants, Sekab and Akzo Nobel.

The sulphite mill produces 240,000 tonnes of dissolving pulp, 17,000 tons of ethanol, and 120,000 tons of lignosulfonates annually, which results in approximately **20,000 tons of fibre sludge waste yearly**. Usually the sludge is used for internal energy production, but due to the low energy content and high moisture of the cellulose containing sludge, it must be used alternatively.

The proposed alternative is a circular renewability and recycling model for the production of Akzo Nobel's Bermocoll, **a high-grade, water soluble polymer that can be used as a paint thickener and a binding agent** in the construction industry. Currently, Akzo Nobel uses 9,000 tons of fossil fuel based ethyl chloride to produce Bermocoll. In an effort to increase Akzo Nobel's product renewability, they will replace their fossil fuel based inputs with bio based cellulose and hemicellulose ethyl chloride (C₂H₅CL) produced by SEKAB from Domsjö Fabriker's ethanol.

FIGURE 37: PRINCIPLE OF CIRCULAR CASE 4

Stakeholders & value chain

The four main stakeholders in Circular Case 4 are located with one kilometre of each other. The first one is **Domsjö Fabriker**, a bio refinery with a wide range of products, all based on renewable and traceable raw materials. They will provide sustainability-sourced wood for the project, process it, and turn their fibre pulp by-product into ethanol. The second stakeholder, **Sekab**, a Swedish firm that specialised in refining biofuels and green chemicals, will convert the bioethanol into ethyl chloride. **Akzo Nobel**, the third stakeholder and leading global paint and specialty chemical company, will use the bio-based ethyl chloride to produce Bermocoll. The fourth stakeholder, **SP Processum**, a Swedish research industry support group, will oversee the project's implementation and support its completion.

Figure 38 presents the value chain and the role of each partner in the circular case 4:

FIGURE 38: VALUE CHAIN AND STAKEHOLDERS OF CIRCULAR CASE 4

The pilot project will use the fibre sludge and hemicellulose sourced from softwood and ordinary baker's yeast will be implemented during the fermentation step. Approximately 200 kg of bioethanol will be produced from 500 kg of fibre sludge. Demonstration of continuous production of 15 kg/day of ethyl chloride from renewable ethanol for 3 weeks to demonstrate the continuous production of 300 kg of ethyl chloride

Through various steps, **Domsjö Fabriker** produces various products including bioethanol, lignin, biogas, and steam. One of the main by-products of this production processes is fibre sludge, which will be used to produce high quality ethanol. For the circular case demonstration, they will produce 200 kg of bioethanol from 500 kg of fibre sludge.

Sekab uses the bioethanol produced by Domsjö Fabriker in addition to solid hydrochloric acid to produce high quality ethyl chloride. They can store up to 300,000 tons of renewable ethanol for different types of chemical processes. For the demonstration phase of the project, they will produce 15 kg of ethyl chloride per day for three weeks to demonstrate their reliability. Once the concept is validated, they will be able to produce 2,000 tonnes of high quality ethyl chloride per year.

Akzo Nobel will replace their current stocks of fossil fuel based ethyl chloride by consuming bio-based ethyl chloride produced by Sekab. Although this will not offset all of their demand, it represents a significant portion depending on Sekab's scale of production. Once they obtain the ethyl chloride, they mix it with ethylene oxide, sodium hydroxide and methylene chloride in a reactor tank and slurry tank, before the product goes in the decanter dryer, grinder, and storage silos. Once the process is complete, the Bermocoll is ready for distribution. Akzo Nobel will secure a new supply of ethyl chloride locally while simultaneously generating a product that is based on renewable materials.

Benefits and Challenges

There are substantial economic and ecological benefits in adopting circular economic models for the production of Bermocoll. Although there are some challenges, they are small enough to warrant a transition from the linear model.

The implementation renewable material in the fermentation process has been shown to increase ethanol production capacity by over 10%, and using recycled resources during the production process **could save 15,390 CO₂eq tonnes of GHG emissions** from entering the atmosphere.

By switching from fossil-fuel based ethyl chloride to a bio based ethyl chloride, Akzo Nobel can improve **its sustainable image** in a competitive industry, known to be non-respectful of the environment.

After the end of the project, the installation of the new plant to produce ethyl chloride would lead to recycle 5,000 tonnes of fibre sludge to produce an additional 2,000 tonnes/year of ethyl chloride with a commercial value of around 4M€ and **landfill fees savings** of 0.35 M€.

The main challenges of the project can be attributed to quality control, supply chain resilience, and economic profitability. Each product (cellulose, ethanol, ethyl chloride, and Bermocoll) will need to be inspected fully to **ensure product quality** and contamination due to the variability of organic inputs. To ensure project resilience, the **reliability of supply streams** to adapt to fluctuating supply and demand pressures must be verified; for example, the price fluctuations in the wood market could result in production inefficiency.

Economic profitability can also be a challenge; it is the driver of the symbiosis, so there must be stable and immediate economic incentives for the project.

<i>Benefit</i>	<i>Quantification</i>	<i>Actor</i>
Ethanol production capacity	10% Increase	Domsjö
CO2 emission prevention	15,390 tonnes	All actors
Ethyl chloride production	2,800 tonne increase	Sekab
Avoided landfill fees	350,000€ savings	Domsjö
Recycled fibre sludge	5,000 tonnes	Domsjö

TABLE 15: ANNUAL SYMBIOSIS BENEFITS

4.5. Circular case 5: PPI and the mining industry in Sweden

Presentation of the Demo case

In the circular case 5, residual Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) from the pulp and paper industry will be used to produce a sealing layer for the mining industry.

GLDs represent a large fraction of waste produced by a sulphate pulp mills. Currently, there are landfilled in Sweden, which is very costly for the PPI.

In parallel, the mining industry tries to minimise its environmental impact by preventing the formation of acid rock drainage (ARD). One way to avoid the formation of ADRs is to limit water and oxygen infiltration, as shown on the following figure. Currently, the sealing layer that limits water and oxygen infiltration is based on an engineered barrier made of clays.

FIGURE 39-SHOWS THE FUNCTION IN THE COVER LAYERS, FOCUSING ON THE SEALING LAYER

After several years of R&D, LTU and SP Processum have shown that the residual GLDs from PPIs can improve the properties of an engineered barrier for the mining industry. The circular case 5 will demonstrate that the whole value chain from producer of GLDs to end user of the sealing layer can be implemented.

The principle of this circular case is represented on Figure 40:

FIGURE 40: PRINCIPLE OF CIRCULAR CASE 5

This demo case is located in the northern parts of Sweden. The mining company Boliden will decide the exact location.

Stakeholders & value chain

Three PAPERCHAIN partners are involved in this Circular Case - SP-Processum (Processum), Boliden Mineral (Boliden) and Lulea Technical University (LTU). They are supported by two Supporting Parties: Ragn-Sells and BillerudKorsnäs. Ragn-Sells will participate as well in the external expert panel.

All of the stakeholders are located in Sweden.

FIGURE 41-SHOWS THE LOCATION OF MAIN STAKEHOLDERS IN SWEDEN

The first partner is **SP-Processum**, a research institute that will coordinate the Case Study, providing the material characterization and monitoring of the Demo.

The second partner is **LTU University** that will plan and evaluate the Demo Case. They will also provide support for dimensioning, testing and monitoring the heavy metals content. LTU is the centre of mining related research and education in Sweden and the home university of the Swedish mining industry.

The third one is **Boliden**, a mining company that will provide site provision and technical assistance in relation with mining procedures and requirements for soil covers, mining waste provision and handling recommendations.

About Supporting Parties, **Ragn-Sells** is a privately held corporate group that is been involved in waste management, environmental services and recycling. Ragn-Sells collect, treat and recycle waste and residual products from businesses, organizations and households.

Ragn-Sells looks forward to collaborating with the PAPERCHAIN Consortium in the search for innovative solutions for the valorisation of the by-product (i.e Green Liquor Dregs, GLD) that Ragn-Sells handle. They will provide GLD for demo activities and also technical support.

Ragn-Sells participates as well in the external expert panel to ensure that the interests of waste management industries are taken into account, that are important for the GLD business (from the pulp and paper industry, via waste management industries, to the mining industry).

In the other cases, the main stakeholders aiming for a sustainable usage for their residual materials are the P&P-industry. No Swedish Paper industry is partner in the project; the recycling company Ragn-Sells will make sure that the correct quality is delivered to the mining site. The mining industries need high quality remediation of their closed mines without resulting in a higher cost.

A simplified summary is given in Figure 42. **In the circular case 5, the PPI produces GLDs. The recycling company collects, quality controls, stores properly and delivers GLDs to the remediation site, where the mining industry uses its function in sealing layers.**

FIGURE 42: VALUE CHAIN AND STAKEHOLDERS OF CIRCULAR CASE 5

Benefits and challenges

PAPERCHAIN will introduce the stakeholders to a **whole new business area**. The P&P-industry does not normally deliver GLDs to the mining industry. The mining industry does not use GLDs in sealing layers today. Ragn-Sells does not currently provide this product of quality controlled GLDs.

It is expected that the market players will find new business models based on circular economy that will **reduce cost/improve profits** for the P&P-Industry and the mining industry. As well the recycling companies can find **new business models to increase their turnover**. Environmentally, there are several benefits: Using waste materials as secondary raw materials, instead of a virgin one (such as bentonite); increasing the quality of remediation of closed mines will **reduce metal leaching**, between other impacts. Socially, the areas of the closed mines will sooner be available to the public to be use as **a natural park for recreation** or other uses.

Main challenges to overcome are about **increasing reliability**. The way of making it real could be by providing to the market players with all results they need to feel comfortable with going forwards on their own. Special focus should be given to the mining industry, to make sure that they consider the technology reliable for them without any single doubt.

5. Conclusions

Circular economy is revolutionizing the global economy. It transforms the lineal model of economy “take, make, use and waste” that is not sustainable anymore for a growing population in a finite resource world. Built on a loop model, the circular economy’s credo relies on four keywords: reduce, reuse, share and recycle.

Concerned by strategic issues such as resource scarcity and slumping economy, Europe was an early adopter of circular economy. Its implementation over the years has been impacted by several factors that are presented in the PESTEL analysis.

On an economic perspective, the implementation of the circular economy is more ambivalent. Although lack of financial incentives represents an important obstacle, different circular economic models are used today. Five different types of circular economic models were identified and described in detail in this report: “product-extension”, “circular supplies”, “resource recovery”, “sharing platforms” and “product as a service”.

A special attention was given to the “resource recovery” model insofar as the five case studies developed in the PaperChain project are developed according to this approach. Through an analysis of industrial examples of circular economy, this study provides best practises (Table 16) that could benefit to the PaperChain demo cases presented in the section 4. This list of best practices is not exhaustive and will be enriched in the next tasks of WP3 based on the explorative process explained at the beginning of this report.

Best Practices	How to implement in PAPERCHAIN
Proximity: Most successful circular model benefit from reducing transportation costs and increasing proximity of operation.	Map the potential partners around the area and assess their respective inputs and outputs to imagine circular partnership
Economic profitability: For full adoption, each circular model needs to be economically sustainable in the long term, especially if a large initial capital investment is required.	All business models must be economic profitability to be sustainable. No exception for circular model. Create scenario and prototypes to assess the economic potential of the solution
Self-organised: Many of the most successful partnerships have evolved organically over several years and local collaboration or fulfil a previously ignored circular model niche.	Revisit your partnership along the years

<p>Production design for by-product re-use:</p> <p>To avoid unnecessary costs and increase final product quality, firms should design their production systems to maintain by-product quality and prevent contamination.</p>	<p>Foreseen obsolescence should be prohibited and replaced by eco-design approach</p>
<p>New opportunity:</p> <p>Circular economy is a driver for innovation. Such approach may offer new opportunity (services, goods, partnership, etc.) and bring solution on multiple level: technical, economic, legal and environmental</p>	<p>Adopt a holistic point of view to imagine how circular economy can transform your company and your business model</p>
<p>Engage with stakeholders:</p> <p>Dialogue with key stakeholders is crucial to develop your branding, reassure investors and prevent some legal issues</p>	<p>Engage dialogue with the local community at an early stage of the project through focus group or visits</p>
<p>Contribute to a circular society:</p> <p>The circular nature of your business should not stop at the end of your production line. A circular approach integer the user experience in a “cradle to cradle” perspective. Such approach could lead to economic benefits</p>	<p>Adopt a holistic approach to integer your clients in the circular economy model developed by the company</p>
<p>Consider the social aspect of the circular business model implemented:</p> <p>Circular economy should not be only economically and environmentally driven but should integer a social dimension to be sustainable</p>	<p>Analyse your circular economy model under a sustainable development scope</p>
<p>Start thinking to the legal barriers as soon as possible</p> <p>Legal constraints can slow down the implementation of a circular economy model</p>	<p>Review legal constraints in targeted countries for the materials considered in the demo cases</p>

TABLE 16: BEST PRACTISES ISSUED FROM THE ANALYSIS OF RESOURCE RECOVERY MODELS

Research carried out through different perspectives enables an analysis of the existing and emerging approaches of circular economy models in the Paper and Pulp Industry. The

results observed in this first deliverable of the PaperChain project pave the way for deeper analysis that would help to characterise the 5 circular models created in PaperChain. Such analysis, which starts in Task 3.2, should take into account those best practices for outlining the building blocks of the reference framework. Some dimensions could be envisioned, such as business, social or policy dimensions. However, there are some other elements that interact in the whole system whose role should be analysed more deeply for designing novel circular models in the PaperChain such as for instance, organizational innovation, technology and innovation process or multi stakeholder involvement.

6. Annexe: Additional examples of circular economic model

Additional examples of company that build their business model on a "product-extension" approach:

Phonebloks	An independent organisation that is helping the mobile phone industry to steer development and production towards products that produce less electronic waste. For now, they are focusing on modular phones that you can easily upgrade, repair and customise. And there is also good news for the customers with two left hands
Miele	The classic long-life model: primary revenue stream from sales of high-grade products with a long useful life. The German domestic appliance company Miele is an example of "Classic Long Life" and "Encourage Sufficiency." The company's primary revenue stream comes from the sales of these high-grade appliances. Miele's washing machines are an almost iconic example of "Classic Long Life" as a business model: their machines are guaranteed a functional lifespan of 20 years, where washing machines on average last some 10 years. Lofthouse and Bhamra (2007) identified the following design strategies employed by Miele: optimal service life (up to 20 years), design for durability, design for upgradability (service engineers can provide software upgrades), reduced energy consumption, and minimized resource use. Hence, business model innovation goes hand in hand with product innovation for circularity.
Vitsoe wall shelving	design for standardisation and compatibility is aimed at countering systemic obsolescence by creating products with parts that fit other products ⁹
Océ-Canon	Document (re)production equipment – Design for disassembly and reassembly is aimed at countering systemic obsolescence by ensuring product parts can be separated and reassembled easily. & Philips Healthcare refurbished systems
Rolls Royce & Philips	Rolls Royce jet engine & Philips pay-per-lux solution
Royal DSM	It reuses materials (a feedstock that was previously considered very low value: co-fermenting sugars derived from crops) and provides new eco-friendly one (cellulosic bioethanol)

Nike - Flyknit technology	Nike - Flyknit technology that creates a shoe upper out of a few single threads. It's less-wasteful (by 80 percent) and better-fitting and lighter—boosting an athlete's performance. Representing a win for the company, a win for the customer and a win for the environment.
The Restart Project (London)	Local economies of repair to minimise material consumption: The Restart Project is a London-based charity and social enterprise which encourages people to use electronic products for longer through a collaborative repair process in which learning and skillsharing opportunities, together with inspirational talks, are offered. In line with his future vision of a 'peoplecentred circular economy', the project has been working to scale-up repair initiatives, organising workshops for new start-ups, offering an international consultation service, and preparing on-line start-up toolkits.
UIW-project	Based on analysis of the cluster cases in the UIW-project, we can distinguish between four generic upgrade business models among the six clusters. We call these the Customized Upgrade, the Modular Upgrade, the Remanufacturing and the Service Upgrade business models. These models differ in the type of added value with which the customer is provided, but also in how this value is produced. Our study also shows that the different business models stress the need for development of digital means in different areas ⁵ .

Additional examples of company that build their business model on a “circular supplies” approach:

Dutch aWEARness'	Worn out garments are collected, shredded and turned into new yarns and new fabric without quality loss. Dutch aWEARness is a young and innovative textile company guided by the principles of sustainable entrepreneurship. It has developed environmentally friendly polyester for clothing manufacturing and offers its clothing accessibility based.
Neste	The Finish refining company, has established in the Netherlands the first bio-LPG production installation in the world. The installation will capture bio-LPG from the side stream gases of its Rotterdam facility that produces biodiesel from various wastes and vegetable oils.

⁵ Simons, M. (2017). Comparing Industrial Cluster Cases to Define Upgrade Business Models for a Circular Economy. In *Dynamics of Long-Life Assets* (pp. 327-356). Springer International Publishing.

Carlsberg	it is worthwhile to look into using completely biodegradable materials. An inspiring example is the Carlsberg's green fibre bottle, made from sustainably sourced wood-fibre that is 100% biodegradable and bio-based, generating zero waste.
Knowwaste	It is tackling a far less appealing waste stream: used nappies. The UK-based company recycles absorbent hygiene products which they collect from washrooms, hospitals, nursing facilities and childcare facilities. They specialise in sterilising and separating the materials to recover plastic and fibre that can then be used to make new products, such as roof tiles, plastic components or fibre-based construction and commercial tubes.
Ecover bottle	The limited-edition Ecover bottle is made from plastic recovered from the ocean and Amsterdam canals. Or the G-star Raw collection made from recovered plastic from the ocean. Both are not only beneficial for the environment, but also very strong marketing campaigns.
CIMV	CIMV developed a revolutionary bio-refinery concept, which enables the recycling of vegetal plant wastes into renewable lignocellulosic plant resources including a phenolic polymer, cellulose and glucose, and sugar syrup.

Additional examples of company that build their business model on a "resource recovery" approach:

Novelis	According to Novelis' 2015 Sustainability Report : "In order to meet the growing demand, Novelis, has made approximately \$2 billion in capital investment in strategic locations, achieving to triple its automotive sheet capacity. During 2015, Novelis opened the world's largest and most technologically advanced aluminium recycling center in Nachterstedt, Germany, expanded their portfolio of certified, high-recycled-content products with the introduction of evercycle™ specialty sheet for food containers and debuted a new, high-recycled-content alloy –designed jointly with Jaguar Land Rover- for the automotive industry. By the end of 2015, Novelis used nearly 50% recycled metal, decreased the water intensity by 22% compared to 2007-2009 average baseline and cut its absolute GHG emissions by 13% in five years, while increasing aluminium production by 5% over the same period. In Novelis they believe that the business case for the circular model is clear, led by significantly improved supply chain efficiency and continuity. The new model means they are less reliant on third
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	<p>party primary aluminum producers and have reduced their reliance on carbon intensive primary aluminum."</p>
SmartCrusher by	<p>"The purpose of SmartCrusher's systems and services is the separation of heterogeneous composite products and waste materials into pure raw materials that are suitable for further use. With the technology presented by SmartCrusher, using the hydrated cement that is released when 'SmartCrushing' the concrete rubble and by using climate-neutral electricity from bio-fuels, cement can be produced 100% CO2-neutral, resulting in closed-loop recycling. As the SmartCrusher does not crush sand and gravel, the cement and hydrated cement will not become polluted by fine broken sand and can straight away be reused to produce new cement/paste. 'Smart Crushing' of concrete rubble does not leave any worthless residual fractions, unlike with traditional processing. Subsequently, the sand and gravel retrieved from concrete rubble, is better in new concrete than new sand and gravel, increasing the strength by 25%, reducing cement approximately 15% and thus reducing CO2 emissions by 15%. SmartCrusher uses about 85% less energy for each processed ton of concrete rubble and is possible to recycle 100% of steel-fibre concrete, while remaining straight, and can be reused straight away."</p>
Kroger	<p>The company used to view the 150 tons of food waste it produces each day as a major cost in terms of lost revenue, disposal fees and emissions. Now, Kroger sees it as a provider of inexpensive and clean energy. That energy powers a 49-acre campus that houses offices as well as the distribution center. The company relies on an "anaerobic digestion" system that converts food waste into biogas that runs the campus's micro turbines and boilers. It replaces virtually all of the natural gas the company previously used to power the distribution center. So far, the initiative has yielded an 18% return on Kroger's investment.</p>
Ricoh	<p>The document management technology manufacturer has an ambitious effort in place to reuse components in printers, scanners and other such equipment when they're retired. Ricoh established a centralized return program across Europe that enables customers to send back used toner cartridges at no charge, and has collection and treatment centers in Europe to handle used service parts after they're replaced.</p>
Starbucks	<p>It is actually aiming to turn thousands of tons of its waste coffee grounds and food into everyday products by using bacteria to generate succinic acid which can then be used in a range of products from detergents to bio-plastics and medicines.</p>

<p>Co-located eco-industrial parks</p>	<p>Kalundborg (1960)</p> <p>Relvão Eco Industrial Park (REIP) (2006)</p> <p>Tianjin TEDA (2005)</p> <p>Shandong Lubei (2003) -It was the biggest ammonium phosphate, sulfate, and cement manufacturing enterprise in China, and was owned by the Lubei Chemical Company Ltd.</p> <p>Xinjiang Shihezi (2002)</p> <p>Guangxi Guigang (2001) - It resulted from efforts to improve an existing park to reduce its high levels of emissions</p> <p>Guangxi Guigang (2001) - It resulted from efforts to improve an existing park to reduce its high levels of emissions</p> <p>Choctaw (1995) - It was developed based on a master plan, and its aim was to solve the significant problem of storing and utilizing shredded tires</p> <p>Kitakyushu (1997) -It was the first eco-industrial park in Japan to recycle and reuse wastes</p>
<p>Virtual eco-industrial park</p>	<p>Styria (1992) - It includes paper-production industries, power plants, cement plants, iron scrap dealers, and a wastewater treatment plant</p>
<p>PROFIBRE (European Innovation Partnership)</p>	<p>PACKAGING PROTECTIVE ELEMENTS (fibre-based protective foams) MADE FROM CELLULOSIC FIBRES (paper waste fraction). As far as the cascade use of wood is concerned the idea in PROFIBRE intends to deviate the part that may go to incineration for energy recovery or to landfilling and address it to new products manufacturing that will contribute to the circular economy giving new uses to both part that comes from the pulp and paper waste and parts that come from the processing of other bio-based and fibre industries.</p>
<p>RUBBERTOMARKET (EIP on Raw Material)</p>	<p>European strategy for market development of innovative use of tyre recycled materials.</p> <p>The drivers of this project are the Tyre Management Companies that are part of this Commitment, and its view are also leading the standardization within the CEN TC 366, in close collaboration with ELTSTANDARD Commitment.</p> <p>The tyre industry is strongly committed to recycle tyres and solutions for the use of recycled rubber in different applications, for this reason we are the main suppliers of end of life tyres to recycling industry in Sweden, Italy, France, Portugal and Spain,</p>

<p>BULKY (EIP on Raw Material)</p>	<p>where any development will directly positive impact on SME in the tyre's recycling industry..</p>
<p>CARBOCYCLE (EIP on Raw Material)</p>	<p>Promotion of the reutilization and valorisation of urban bulky wastes as alternative sustainable source to innovative applications.</p> <p>Urban bulky waste is a very heterogeneous material flow usually destined to landfill. The idea here is to improve the end-of-life and disposal of these complex products, proposing and demonstrating the viability of a new collection stream model with integrated advanced technology treatments to increase the quantity and quality of recovered materials, substituting other raw materials with highest environmental impact. Reusing furniture or valuable components; Separating and recovering valuable materials, i.e. wood, plastics, foams, textiles, metals.etc.</p> <p>Main objective is to define, industrialize and bring to market a Recycling Process for CFRP (Carbon Fibres Reinforced Plastic) at diverse stages of life cycle (Scrap & End-of-Life parts) that represent a resource to substitute Industrial applications and Natural Graphite (NG), a Critical Raw Material currently imported for a portion exceeding 70%, (from a single Country: China), while CFRP Products are just disposed in Landfill.</p> <p>This objective counts on intermediate targets, namely the screening of NG properties required by current applications, agreements with NG industry, detailed analysis of all applications in Transport, Energy and Retail sectors and finally the development of a recycling business model for CFRP waste at the most relevant sources, sorting for quality and supply availability.</p>

Additional examples of company that build their business model on a "sharing platform" approach:

<p>Kierrätysverkko</p>	<p>VALUE PROPOSITION:</p> <p>End users: One stop shopping for used goods and one stop recycling. Society: Putting human and physical resources into more efficient use.</p> <p>MAIN CUSTOMERS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Individuals who want to get rid of unwanted items. 2) Individuals interested in buying used goods <p>REVENUE GENERATION LOGIC: Kierrätysverkko Oy receives a provision on the goods sold at the recycling center</p>
<p>Venuu</p>	<p>VALUE PROPOSITION:</p>

	<p>1) End users: Find new and exciting venues quickly and without a hassle.</p> <p>2) Venue providers: By using Venuu you will reduce your risk and bring in more customers.</p> <p>MAIN CUSTOMERS: Venue providers and event organizers</p> <p>REVENUE GENERATION LOGIC: Venue providers pay a commission for each time a venue is rented via Venuu.fi.</p>
FOOD	Kuhteilen, Eat With Me, WeFarm (Google, Telefonica and others), P2P Food Lab (Sony CSL)
FINANCIAL	Finpoint, Lendico, openforum (Bank of America), Crowdfunding (Volksbank Bühl)
MOBILITY	Uber, Getaround, car2go (Daimler), Parkatmyhouse (BMW)

Additional examples of company that build their business model on a “product as a service” approach:

Daimler	<p>According to an article by Computerworld: “Daimler realized that its batteries from electronic vehicles are after 10 years still useable and of value for generating energy. The batteries will not be able to deliver the same capacity, however by using the batteries in a large energy storage system, Daimler is able to provide the batteries with a second life. Daimler installs a large energy storage system in Germany using reused batteries of electronic vehicles. Taking into account a small decrease in the capacity of the batteries, about 1000 batteries are needed to generate a storage capacity of 13 million watt hour (MWh).The reused batteries for example support in the city of Lünen the electricity network by capturing surplus from generated wind power. The reuse of the batteries will not only keep them out of landfills, but will help reduce costs in the EV marketplace by adding an additional revenue stream.”(Computerworld, viewed at 20/12/15, http://www.computerworld.com/article/3005757/sustainable-it/daimler-to-recycle-electric-car-batteries-for-massive-energy-storage-systems.html)</p>
Desso	<p>Desso is supplying carpets to commercial customers. Instead of conventionally selling their product, they lease their carpet to the users. Through leasing Desso offers a full service to its customers including installation, cleaning, maintenance and eventually removal. The company owns the product and at the end of its life, the carpet is collected and recycled in to new carpet, which will be leased again. Via this leasing construction collection of old carpets, it positively contributes to closing the loop.</p>
Koppert	<p>Koppert, a pesticide company, switched to selling a pest-free crop. They take care of spraying and the proper application of the pesticides.</p>

Because of this, they were able to switch to organic pest controls, which are more cost effective if you have the skills to apply them. So this is a double win: Koppert hired staff specialising in organic pest control and developed a really good business case. They did especially well with greenhouses, of which we have so many in the Netherlands.

RePack / Peruste Oy Repack is a Finnish packaging materials manufacturing company that wants to reduce the amount of trash by introducing an alternative to disposable packaging materials: reusable delivery packages. Furthermore, Repack has developed a truly interesting business model. The company doesn't sell the delivery packages it produces, but rents them out for companies. By renting reusable packages instead of selling disposable ones, the company makes sure that the packages come back and remain in use. In this way Repack also contributes to the development of a circular economy.

Nurmi Clothing Sustainable clothing + a clothing rental service. Nurmi Clothing uses fabrics and production processes that are less harmful to the environment compared to most other clothing companies. Nurmi Clothing is also experimenting with a clothing rental service.

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